

Dawn VIR Sequence report for Vesta Science HAMO 2 (VH2) (vir_da030)

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ABSTRACT

This document constitutes the official flight operation report for the VIR (Visible and Infrared Mapping Spectrometer) instrument onboard the Dawn spacecraft, specifically covering the commanding and sequencing activities performed for the vir_da030 session. These operations were executed as part of the VH2 phase.

The mission profile focused on the observational sequences for the characterization of the planetary body Vesta, aiming to map its mineralogical features and surface properties.

The report details the generation of the instrument's commanding sequences and the formal verification process. All sequences have been checked against the mission's flight and guideline rules within the SASF (Spacecraft Activity Sequence File) framework. Furthermore, the VIR SASF files were successfully integrated with the sequences of the other onboard instruments to ensure system-level compatibility and resource management. The final integrated sequences were successfully uploaded and executed on the spacecraft during the scheduled vir_da030 window.

KEYWORDS

VIR • Spectral Instrument • Dawn NASA Mission

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References

- [1] M. de Sanctis *et al.*, "The VIR Spectrometer," *ISSR*, vol. 163, no. 1–4, pp. 329–369, Dec. 2011, doi: 10.1007/s11214-010-9668-5.
- [2] A. K. J. Stipanuk, "Spacecraft Activity Sequence File (SASF) Interface.," *Deep Space Mission System (DSMS) Subsystem Software Interface Specification*, 2004.

1. Check list of the sequence vir_vh2_C5HAMO2.r04.sasf

The following table presents the checklist of the validation tests performed on the vir_vh2_C5HAMO2.r04.sasf sequence. The OK column indicates successful test execution, while the NA (Not Applicable) column denotes tests that are not relevant to this specific sequence. The P (Pending) column identifies tests that have failed or require further resolution. The Item column serves as a unique identifier for each performed test, and the Description column provides a concise summary of the specific verification criteria.

OK	NA	P	Item	Description
Flight Rules				
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	F-VIRC09	VIR cryocooler cool down time
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	F-VIRC10	VIR cover actuation time
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	F-VIRC11	Allow enough time for VIR to transition to STAND_BY after a SCIENCE mode
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	F-VIRC12	Allow enough time for VIR to STAND_BY after issuing VIR_MM_DUMP command
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	F-VIRA16	VIR timing requirements for repetition time and integration time
Guideline				
Syntax and grammar analysis				
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	G-VIRO1	Syntax and grammar analysis
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	G-VIRO2	File name and revision number
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	G-VIRO3	The execution of the sequence occurs within the time boundaries (APPLICABLE-(START&STOP)-TIME)
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	G-VIRO4	BEGIN and CUTOFF are equal to boundaries
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	G-VIRO5	Required of VML_START
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	G-VIRO6	if VML_START, file buffer loaded (d:/fb05)
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	G-VIRO7	Numerical parameters are in the range
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	G-VIRO8	String parameters are in the range
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	G-VIRO9	Integration time and delay time are such that the two channels window timing are centered
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	G-VIR10	Do not use epochs_labels different from those defined in EPOCH_DEF
Running and simulating of the sequence				
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	G-VIR11	No duplicates found in the list of requests names
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	G-VIR12	VIR Mode transition
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	G-VIR13	All VIR command have time for execution
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	G-VIR14	There are partial dumps
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	G-VIR15	No time overlap between the requests
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	G-VIR16	Cover open during Science acquisition
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	G-VIR17	There are critical commands accepted
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	G-VIR18	Cryocooler used only when need
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	G-VIR19	When using VIR_SAFE or VIR_TC_MM_CONF is required the Mass Memory to have all pages empty
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	G-VIR20	Avoid MM overflow

1.1 List of operations

The following table details the operational operations executed within the vir_vh2_C5HAMO2.r04.sasf sequence. For each operation, the start time, stop time, and duration (expressed in seconds) are reported.

Request Name	Start Time[s]	Stop Time[s]	Duration[s]
VIR_VH2_VMLSTART_C5HAMO2	0	2	2
VIR_VH2_C5OpenCover_001	0	40	40
VIR_VH2_C5OffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_001	0	3482	3482
VIR_VH2_C5CloseCover_001	0	38	38
VIR_VH2_C5DumpDataToVR4_001	0	9601	9601
VIR_VH2_C5FullCalibNoCooling_001	0	1817	1817
VIR_VH2_C5OpenCover_002	0	40	40
VIR_VH2_C5OffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_002	0	3482	3482
VIR_VH2_C5CloseCover_002	0	38	38
VIR_VH2_C5DumpDataToVR4_002	0	9601	9601
VIR_VH2_C5OpenCover_003	0	40	40
VIR_VH2_C5OffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_003	0	3482	3482
VIR_VH2_C5CloseCover_003	0	38	38
VIR_VH2_C5DumpDataToVR4_003	0	9601	9601
VIR_VH2_C5OpenCover_004	0	40	40
VIR_VH2_C5OffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_004	0	3482	3482
VIR_VH2_C5CloseCover_004	0	38	38
VIR_VH2_C5DumpDataToVR4_004	0	9601	9601
VIR_VH2_C5OpenCover_005	0	40	40
VIR_VH2_C5OffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_005	0	3482	3482
VIR_VH2_C5CloseCover_005	0	38	38
VIR_VH2_C5DumpDataToVR4_005	0	9601	9601
VIR_VH2_C5OpenCover_006	0	40	40
VIR_VH2_C5OffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_006	0	3482	3482
VIR_VH2_C5CloseCover_006	0	38	38
VIR_VH2_C5DumpDataToVR4_006	0	9601	9601
VIR_VH2_C5OpenCover_007	0	40	40
VIR_VH2_C5OffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_007	0	3482	3482
VIR_VH2_C5CloseCover_007	0	38	38
VIR_VH2_C5DumpDataToVR4_007	0	9601	9601
VIR_VH2_C5OpenCover_008	0	40	40
VIR_VH2_C5OffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_008	0	3482	3482
VIR_VH2_C5CloseCover_008	0	38	38
VIR_VH2_C5DumpDataToVR4_008	0	9601	9601
VIR_VH2_C5OpenCover_009	0	40	40
VIR_VH2_C5OffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_009	0	3482	3482
VIR_VH2_C5CloseCover_009	0	38	38
VIR_VH2_C5DumpDataToVR4_009	0	9601	9601
VIR_VH2_C5OpenCover_010	0	40	40
VIR_VH2_C5OffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_010	0	3482	3482

VIR_VH2_C5CloseCover_010	0	38	38
VIR_VH2_C5DumpDataToVR4_010	0	9601	9601
VIR_VH2_VMLEND_C5HAMO2	0	1	1

1.2 Memories usage

Ecco la traduzione in inglese tecnico-scientifico, ottimizzata per la descrizione di grafici di telemetria e occupazione dati:

Technical English Translation The following plots illustrate the data volume and memory occupancy for both the VIR infrared (IR) and visible (VIS) channels. The transitions between the various instrument operational modes are indicated by the green vertical lines.

2. Check list of the sequence vir_vh2_C6HAMO2.r04.sasf

The following table presents the checklist of the validation tests performed on the vir_vh2_C6HAMO2.r04.sasf sequence. The OK column indicates successful test execution, while the NA (Not Applicable) column denotes tests that are not relevant to this specific sequence. The P (Pending) column identifies tests that have failed or require further resolution. The Item column serves as a unique identifier for each performed test, and the Description column provides a concise summary of the specific verification criteria.

OK	NA	P	Item	Description
Flight Rules				
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	F-VIRC09	VIR cryocooler cool down time
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	F-VIRC10	VIR cover actuation time
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	F-VIRC11	Allow enough time for VIR to transition to STAND_BY after a SCIENCE mode
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	F-VIRC12	Allow enough time for VIR to STAND_BY after issuing VIR_MM_DUMP command
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	F-VIRA16	VIR timing requirements for repetition time and integration time
Guideline				
Syntax and grammar analysis				
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	G-VIRO1	Syntax and grammar analysis
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	G-VIRO2	File name and revision number
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	G-VIRO3	The execution of the sequence occurs within the time boundaries (APPLICABLE-(START&STOP)-TIME)
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	G-VIRO4	BEGIN and CUTOFF are equal to boundaries
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	G-VIRO5	Required of VML_START
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	G-VIRO6	if VML_START, file buffer loaded (d:/fb05)
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	G-VIRO7	Numerical parameters are in the range
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	G-VIRO8	String parameters are in the range
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	G-VIRO9	Integration time and delay time are such that the two channels window timing are centered
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	G-VIR10	Do not use epochs_labels different from those defined in EPOCH_DEF
Running and simulating of the sequence				
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	G-VIR11	No duplicates found in the list of requests names
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	G-VIR12	VIR Mode transition
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	G-VIR13	All VIR command have time for execution
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	G-VIR14	There are partial dumps
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	G-VIR15	No time overlap between the requests
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	G-VIR16	Cover open during Science acquisition
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	G-VIR17	There are critical commands accepted
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	G-VIR18	Cryocooler used only when need
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	G-VIR19	When using VIR_SAFE or VIR_TC_MM_CONF is required the Mass Memory to have all pages empty
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	G-VIR20	Avoid MM overflow

2.1 List of operations

The following table details the operational operations executed within the vir_vh2_C6HAMO2.r04.sasf sequence. For each operation, the start time, stop time, and duration (expressed in seconds) are reported.

Request Name	Start Time[s]	Stop Time[s]	Duration[s]
VIR_VH2_VMLSTART_C6HAMO2	0	2	2
VIR_VH2_C6OpenCover_001	0	40	40
VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_001	0	1735	1735
VIR_VH2_C6CloseCover_001	0	38	38
VIR_VH2_C6DumpDataToVR4_001	0	7201	7201
VIR_VH2_C6FullCalibNoCooling_001	0	1817	1817
VIR_VH2_C6OpenCover_002	0	40	40
VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_002	0	1735	1735
VIR_VH2_C6CloseCover_002	0	38	38
VIR_VH2_C6DumpDataToVR4_002	0	7201	7201
VIR_VH2_C6OpenCover_003	0	40	40
VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_003	0	1735	1735
VIR_VH2_C6CloseCover_003	0	38	38
VIR_VH2_C6DumpDataToVR4_003	0	7201	7201
VIR_VH2_C6OpenCover_004	0	40	40
VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_004	0	1735	1735
VIR_VH2_C6CloseCover_004	0	38	38
VIR_VH2_C6DumpDataToVR4_004	0	7201	7201
VIR_VH2_C6OpenCover_005	0	40	40
VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_005	0	1735	1735
VIR_VH2_C6CloseCover_005	0	38	38
VIR_VH2_C6DumpDataToVR4_005	0	7201	7201
VIR_VH2_C6OpenCover_006	0	40	40
VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_006	0	1735	1735
VIR_VH2_C6CloseCover_006	0	38	38
VIR_VH2_C6DumpDataToVR4_006	0	7201	7201
VIR_VH2_C6OpenCover_007	0	40	40
VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_007	0	1735	1735
VIR_VH2_C6CloseCover_007	0	38	38
VIR_VH2_C6DumpDataToVR4_007	0	7201	7201
VIR_VH2_C6OpenCover_008	0	40	40
VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_008	0	1735	1735
VIR_VH2_C6CloseCover_008	0	38	38
VIR_VH2_C6DumpDataToVR4_008	0	7201	7201
VIR_VH2_C6OpenCover_009	0	40	40
VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_009	0	1735	1735
VIR_VH2_C6CloseCover_009	0	38	38
VIR_VH2_C6DumpDataToVR4_009	0	7201	7201
VIR_VH2_C6OpenCover_010	0	40	40
VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_010	0	1735	1735

VIR_VH2_C6CloseCover_010	0	38	38
VIR_VH2_C6DumpDataToVR4_010	0	7201	7201
VIR_VH2_C6PowerOff_010	0	-54032159	-54032159
VIR_VH2_VMLEND_C6HAMO2	0	1	1

2.2 Memories usage

Ecco la traduzione in inglese tecnico-scientifico, ottimizzata per la descrizione di grafici di telemetria e occupazione dati:

Technical English Translation The following plots illustrate the data volume and memory occupancy for both the VIR infrared (IR) and visible (VIS) channels. The transitions between the various instrument operational modes are indicated by the green vertical lines.

3. Integrated sequence: da030a.00.filter.rs0e

The following table presents the checklist of the validation tests performed on the da030a.00.filter.rs0e sequence. The OK column indicates successful test execution, while the NA (Not Applicable) column denotes tests that are not relevant to this specific sequence. The P (Pending) column identifies tests that have failed or require further resolution. The Item column serves as a unique identifier for each performed test, and the Description column provides a concise summary of the specific verification criteria.

The VIR instrument was configured to acquire 4 calibration cubes and 150 cubes for IR channel and 150 for VIS channel.

OK	NA	P	Item	Description
Flight Rules				
✓	□	□	F-VIRC09	VIR cryocooler cool down time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC10	VIR cover actuation time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC11	Allow enough time for VIR to transition to STAND_BY after a SCIENCE mode
✓	□	□	F-VIRC12	Allow enough time for VIR to STAND_BY after issuing VIR_MM_DUMP command
✓	□	□	F-VIRA16	VIR timing requirements for repetition time and integration time
Guideline				
Running and simulating of the sequence				
✓	□	□	G-VIR12	VIR Mode transition
✓	□	□	G-VIR13	All VIR command have time for execution
✓	□	□	G-VIR14	There are partial dumps
✓	□	□	G-VIR15	No time overlap between the requests
✓	□	□	G-VIR16	Cover open during Science acquisition
✓	□	□	G-VIR17	There are critical commands accepted
✓	□	□	G-VIR18	Cryocooler used only when need

4. Appendix

This appendix contains the SASF (Spacecraft Activity Sequence File) sequences referenced in this report, along with the SPICE meta-kernel employed for the geometric computations and reference frame transformations.

The following SASF files were processed:

4.1 The sequence: vir_vh2_C5HAMO2.r04.sasf

1	CCSD3ZF0000100000001NJPL3KS0L015\$MARK\$;	sasf
2	MISSION_NAME = DAWN;	
3	SPACECRAFT_NAME = DAWN;	
4	DATA_SET_ID = SPACECRAFT_ACTIVITY_SEQUENCE_DSC;	
5	FILE_NAME = vir_vh2_C5HAMO2.r04.sasf;	
6	APPLICABLE_START_TIME = 2012-196T15:31:14.000;	
7	APPLICABLE_STOP_TIME = 2012-201T16:56:47.000;	
8	PRODUCT_CREATION_TIME = 2012-163T05:55:02.000;	
9	PRODUCER_ID = SEQ;	
10	SEQ_ID = vir_vh2_C5HAMO2.r04;	
11	HOST_ID = dawnjpldsc;	
12	CCSD3RE00000\$MARK\$NJPL3IF0M01300000001;	
13	\$\$DWN SPACECRAFT ACTIVITY SEQUENCE FILE	
14	*****	
15	*PROJECT DWN	
16	*SPACECRAFT 203	
17	*OPERATOR DWNDSC team account	
18	*FILE_CMPLT TRUE	
19	*DATE Mon Jun 11 05:55:02 2012	
20	*seqgenCore V32.0 Tue Dec 14 17:21:23 PST 2010	
21	*BEGIN 2012-196T15:31:14.000	
22	*CUTOFF 2012-201T16:56:47.000	
23	*TITLE VIR_VH2_da030_Cycle_5_ds120	
24	*EPOCHS_DEF	
25	*EPOCHS_END	
26	*Input files used:	
27	*File Type Last modified File name	
28	*SC_MODEL Tue Apr 10 18:57:18 2012 /delivery/MSOP/J6.7.1-DAWN/seq/smf/dawn.cd1.FDAWN_9_0DDAWN_9_0_0_2012Apr10_11_56_00.smf	
29	*CATALOG Wed Mar 14 19:26:38 2012 /delivery/MSOP/J6.7.1-DAWN/seq/satf/dawn.cd1.FDAWN_9_0DDAWN_9_0_0_2012Mar14_1200_1.satf	
30	*LEGENDS Tue May 11 21:36:07 1999 /delivery/MSOP/J6.7.1-DAWN/seq/legend/Dawn.1.0.legend	
31	*CATALOG Thu Mar 24 16:44:44 2011 /delivery/MSOP/J6.7.1-DAWN/seq/satf/dawn.blk.d_fb20_eng_blib_mod.900.r4.satf	
32	*CATALOG Thu May 20 15:12:56 2010 /delivery/MSOP/J6.7.1-DAWN/seq/satf/dawn.blk.d_fb19_sci_blib_mod.900.r3.satf	
33	*CATALOG Thu May 20 15:12:39 2010 /delivery/MSOP/J6.7.1-DAWN/seq/satf/dawn.blk.d_fb17_safe_blib_mod.900.r2.satf	
34	*CONTEXT Thu May 24 20:41:12 2007 /delivery/MSOP/J6.7.1-DAWN/seq/cvf/dawn.sct.cvf	
35	*CONTEXT Wed Mar 14 17:36:14 2012 /delivery/MSOP/J6.7.1-DAWN/seq/cvf/dawn.cvf	
36	*CONTEXT Mon Mar 12 17:15:57 2007 /delivery/MSOP/J6.7.1-DAWN/seq/cvf/msop.soe.cvf	
37	*CONTEXT Mon Apr 21 19:28:05 2003 /delivery/MSOPRW/J6.7.1-DAWN/seq_rw/seq_config/dsn_config/msop.dsn.cvf	
38	*CONTEXT Thu Aug 4 18:09:05 2011 /delivery/MSOPRW/J6.7.1-DAWN/seq_rw/seq_config/dsn_config/soe_defaults_203.cvf	
39	*CONTEXT Thu Aug 2 15:59:05 2007 /delivery/MSOPRW/J6.7.1-DAWN/seq_rw/seq_config/dsn_config/dsn_config.cvf	
40	*CONTEXT Thu Jun 7 18:59:41 2012 /export/home/dwndsc/dsc/sequencing/vesta/vh2/optg_vesta_DA029_DA030_v1.cvf	

```

41 *CLOCK      Thu Apr 26 16:26:35 2012 /delivery/MSOPRW/J6.7.1-DAWN/seq_rw/seq_input/sclk/
DAWN_203_PSCLKSCET.00003
42 *SEQUENCE  Mon Jun 11 05:55:02 2012 /export/home/dwndsc/dsc/sequencing/vesta/vh2/da030/vir/r04/
vir_vh2_C5HAMO2.r04.sasf
43 *ALLOCATION
44 *BG_SEQUENCE
45 *CAT_NO_VML
46 *CONDITIONS
47 *DEFINITION
48 *DEP_CONTEXT
49 *EVENTS
50 *LIGHTTIME
51 *MASK
52 *OPTG_FD
53 *GEOMETRY
54 *REDUNDANT
55 *REQUESTS
56 *RESOLUTION
57 *RULES
58 *SCRIPT
59 *ON_BOARD_SE
60 *TELEMETRY
61 *TYPEDEF
62 *VIEWPERIOD
63 *VIEW_FD
64 *****
65 $$E0H
66 $$E0D
67 request(VIR_VH2_VMLSTART_C5HAMO2,
68     START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_058+02:07:00,
69     TITLE, "VIR Sequence Start - vir_vh2_C5HAMO2 (ds120)",
70     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
71     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
72     KEY, "No_Key")
73
74     activity(1,
75     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
76     SEQTRAN_directive(VML_START,2000-001T00:00:00.000,2050-001T00:00:00.000,"ABSLTE","vir_vh2_C5HAMO2","v
fb04")
77     ),
78     note(1,
79     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
80     TEXT,\ "Begin sequence ds120 - vir_vh2_C5HAMO2"\
81     ),
82     end;
83
84     request(VIR_VH2_C50openCover_001,
85     START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_058+02:08:00,
86     TITLE, "VIR open cover",
87     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
88     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
89     KEY, "No_Key")
90
91     activity(1,
92     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
93     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50openCover_001: Set for opening the cover."\,
94     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")

```

```
95  ),
96  end;
97
98  request(VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_001,
99  START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_058+02:10:00,
100  TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
101  REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
102  PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
103  KEY, "No_Key")
104
105  command(1,
106  SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
107  NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
  detector,52 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
108  VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,51,30,77,175,5,52,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
109  ),
110  command(2,
111  SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
112  COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
113  NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
114  VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
115  ),
116  command(3,
117  SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:48\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
118  NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
119  VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
120  ),
121  note(1,
122  SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
123  TEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.181 Gibit"\
124  ),
125  command(4,
126  SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
127  NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
  detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
128  VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
129  ),
130  command(5,
131  SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
132  COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
133  NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
134  VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
135  ),
136  command(6,
137  SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
138  NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
139  VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
140  ),
141  note(2,
142  SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
143  TEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.355 Gibit"\
144  ),
145  command(7,
146  SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
147  NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
  detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
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148     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
149 ),
150     command(8,
151         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
152         COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
153         NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
154         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
155     ),
156     command(9,
157         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
158         NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
159         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
160     ),
161     note(3,
162         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
163         TEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.529 Gibit\"\\
164     ),
165     command(10,
166         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
167         NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
168         detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\\,
169     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
170 ),
171     command(11,
172         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
173         COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
174         NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
175         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
176     ),
177     command(12,
178         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
179         NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
180         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
181     ),
182     note(4,
183         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
184         TEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 0.703 Gibit\"\\
185     ),
186     command(13,
187         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
188         NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
189         detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\\,
190     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
191 ),
192     command(14,
193         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
194         COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
195         NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
196         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
197     ),
198     command(15,
199         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
200         NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
201         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
202     ),
```

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201  note(5,
202    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
203    TEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.5 Data Volume in MM 0.877 Gibit\"
204  ),
205  command(16,
206    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
207    NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
208      detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\",
209    VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR_TM
210  ),
211  command(17,
212    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
213    COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"
214    NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\",
215    VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
216  ),
217  command(18,
218    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
219    NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"
220    VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
221  ),
222  note(6,
223    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
224    TEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.6 Data Volume in MM 1.051 Gibit\"
225  ),
226  command(19,
227    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
228    NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
229      detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\",
230    VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR_TM
231  ),
232  command(20,
233    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
234    COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"
235    NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\",
236    VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
237  ),
238  command(21,
239    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
240    NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"
241    VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
242  ),
243  note(7,
244    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
245    TEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.7 Data Volume in MM 1.225 Gibit\"
246  ),
247  command(22,
248    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
249    NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
250      detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\",
251    VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR_TM
252  ),
253  command(23,
254    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
255    COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"
```

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253     NTEXT, \"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\",
254     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
255 ),
256     command(24,
257     SCHEDULED_TIME, \00:05:36, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
258     NTEXT, \"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\",
259     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
260 ),
261     note(8,
262     SCHEDULED_TIME, \00:00:05, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
263     TEXT, \"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.8 Data Volume in MM 1.399 Gibit\"
264 ),
265     command(25,
266     SCHEDULED_TIME, \00:00:01, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
267     NTEXT, \"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
268     detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\",
269     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,\"IR_VIS\", \"ALL_SUBFRAMES\", \"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR_TM
270 ),
271     command(26,
272     SCHEDULED_TIME, \00:00:05, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
273     COMMENT, \"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\",
274     NTEXT, \"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\",
275     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
276 ),
277     command(27,
278     SCHEDULED_TIME, \00:05:36, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
279     NTEXT, \"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\",
280     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
281 ),
282     note(9,
283     SCHEDULED_TIME, \00:00:05, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
284     TEXT, \"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.9 Data Volume in MM 1.573 Gibit\"
285 ),
286     command(28,
287     SCHEDULED_TIME, \00:00:01, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
288     NTEXT, \"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
289     detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\",
290     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,\"IR_VIS\", \"ALL_SUBFRAMES\", \"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR_TM
291 ),
292     command(29,
293     SCHEDULED_TIME, \00:00:05, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
294     COMMENT, \"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\",
295     NTEXT, \"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\",
296     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
297 ),
298     command(30,
299     SCHEDULED_TIME, \00:05:36, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
300     NTEXT, \"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\",
301     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
302 ),
303     note(10,
304     SCHEDULED_TIME, \00:00:05, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
305     TEXT, \"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.10 Data Volume in MM 1.746 Gibit\"
306 ),
307     end;
```

```
307 request(VIR_VH2_C5CloseCover_001,
308     START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_058+03:09:00,
309     TITLE, "VIR close cover",
310     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
311     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
312     KEY, "No_Key")
313
314 activity(1,
315     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
316     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C5CloseCover_001: Set for closing the cover." \,
317     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"CLOSE")
318 ),
319 end;
320
321 request(VIR_VH2_C5DumpDataToVR4_001,
322     START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_058+06:28:00,
323     TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",
324     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
325     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
326     KEY, "No_Key")
327
328 command(1,
329     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
330     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C5DumpDataToVR4_001: begin data dumping into VR4." \,
331     VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
332 ),
333 command(2,
334     SCHEDULED_TIME,\02:39:55\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
335     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C5DumpDataToVR4_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
336     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
337 ),
338 note(1,
339     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
340     TEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C5DumpDataToVR4_001: data volume in VR4 1.279 Gibit." \
341 ),
342 end;
343
344 request(VIR_VH2_C5FullCalibNoCooling_001,
345     START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_058+11:18:40,
346     TITLE, "VIR full calibration sequence",
347     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
348     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
349     KEY, "No_Key")
350
351 command(1,
352     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
353     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C5FullCalibNoCooling_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY" \,
354     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
355 ),
356 command(2,
357     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
358     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C5FullCalibNoCooling_001: perform the internal full calibration" \,
359     VIR_CALIBRATION("H_SPE_H_SPA_F", "CLOSECOVERATEND", "FULLCALSEQ")
360 ),
361 command(3,
362     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:15:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
363     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C5FullCalibNoCooling_001: begin data dumping into VR4." \,
```

```
364 VIR_MM_DUMP("NO_COMPRESSION")
365 ),
366 command(4,
367 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:15:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
368 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C5FullCalibNoCooling_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY"\,
369 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
370 ),
371 note(1,
372 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
373 TEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C5FullCalibNoCooling_001: full calibration is finished."\
374 ),
375 note(2,
376 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
377 TEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C5FullCalibNoCooling_001: Data Volume in VR4: 0.126 Gibit,120 pages, 15960
packets."\
378 ),
379 end;
380
381 request(VIR_VH2_C50penCover_002,
382 START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_059+02:28:00,
383 TITLE, "VIR open cover",
384 REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
385 PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
386 KEY, "No_Key")
387
388 activity(1,
389 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
390 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50penCover_002: Set for opening the cover."\,
391 VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
392 ),
393 end;
394
395 request(VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_002,
396 START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_059+02:30:00,
397 TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
398 REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
399 PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
400 KEY, "No_Key")
401
402 command(1,
403 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
404 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_002: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
detector,52 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
405 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,51,30,77,175,5,52,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
406 ),
407 command(2,
408 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
409 COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
410 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_002: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
411 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
412 ),
413 command(3,
414 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:48\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
415 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
416 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
417 ),
418 note(1,
```

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419     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
420     TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_002: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.181 Gibit"\
421     ),
422     command(4,
423     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
424     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_002: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
425     detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
426     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
427     ),
428     command(5,
429     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
430     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
431     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_002: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
432     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
433     ),
434     command(6,
435     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
436     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
437     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
438     ),
439     note(2,
440     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
441     TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_002: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.355 Gibit"\
442     ),
443     command(7,
444     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
445     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_002: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
446     detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
447     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
448     ),
449     command(8,
450     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
451     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
452     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_002: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
453     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
454     ),
455     command(9,
456     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
457     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
458     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
459     ),
460     note(3,
461     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
462     TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_002: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.529 Gibit"\
463     ),
464     command(10,
465     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
466     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_002: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
467     detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
468     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
469     ),
470     command(11,
471     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
472     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
473     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_002: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
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471     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
472   ),
473   command(12,
474     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
475     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
476     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
477   ),
478   note(4,
479     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
480     TEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_002: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 0.703 Gibit" \
481   ),
482   command(13,
483     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
484     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_002: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
485     detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s" \,
486     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
487   ),
488   command(14,
489     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
490     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714" \,
491     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_002: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode" \,
492     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
493   ),
494   command(15,
495     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
496     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
497     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
498   ),
499   note(5,
500     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
501     TEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_002: Cube N.5 Data Volume in MM 0.877 Gibit" \
502   ),
503   command(16,
504     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
505     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_002: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
506     detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s" \,
507     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
508   ),
509   command(17,
510     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
511     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714" \,
512     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_002: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode" \,
513     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
514   ),
515   command(18,
516     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
517     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
518     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
519   ),
520   note(6,
521     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
522     TEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_002: Cube N.6 Data Volume in MM 1.051 Gibit" \
523   ),
524   command(19,
525     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
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524 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_002: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
525 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
526 ),
527 command(20,
528 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
529 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
530 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_002: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
531 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
532 ),
533 command(21,
534 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
535 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
536 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
537 ),
538 note(7,
539 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
540 TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_002: Cube N.7 Data Volume in MM 1.225 Gibit"\
541 ),
542 command(22,
543 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
544 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_002: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
545 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
546 ),
547 command(23,
548 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
549 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
550 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_002: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
551 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
552 ),
553 command(24,
554 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
555 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
556 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
557 ),
558 note(8,
559 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
560 TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_002: Cube N.8 Data Volume in MM 1.399 Gibit"\
561 ),
562 command(25,
563 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
564 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_002: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
565 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
566 ),
567 command(26,
568 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
569 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
570 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_002: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
571 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
572 ),
573 command(27,
574 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
575 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
```

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576     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
577   ),
578   note(9,
579     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
580     TEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_002: Cube N.9 Data Volume in MM 1.573 Gibit"\
581   ),
582   command(28,
583     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
584     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_002: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
585       detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
586     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
587   ),
588   command(29,
589     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
590     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
591     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_002: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
592     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
593   ),
594   command(30,
595     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
596     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
597     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
598   ),
599   note(10,
600     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
601     TEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_002: Cube N.10 Data Volume in MM 1.746 Gibit"\
602   ),
603 end;
604 request(VIR_VH2_C5CloseCover_002,
605   START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_059+03:30:00,
606   TITLE, "VIR close cover",
607   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
608   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
609   KEY, "No_Key")
610
611 activity(1,
612   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
613   NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C5CloseCover_002: Set for closing the cover.""\,
614   VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"CLOSE")
615 ),
616 end;
617
618 request(VIR_VH2_C5DumpDataToVR4_002,
619   START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_059+06:28:00,
620   TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",
621   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
622   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
623   KEY, "No_Key")
624
625 command(1,
626   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
627   NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C5DumpDataToVR4_002: begin data dumping into VR4.""\,
628   VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
629 ),
630 command(2,
631   SCHEDULED_TIME,\02:39:55\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
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632     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C5DumpDataToVR4_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
633     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
634   ),
635   note(1,
636     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
637     TEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C5DumpDataToVR4_002: data volume in VR4 1.398 Gibit." \
638   ),
639   end;
640
641   request(VIR_VH2_C50penCover_003,
642     START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_060+02:08:00,
643     TITLE, "VIR open cover",
644     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
645     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
646     KEY, "No_Key")
647
648   activity(1,
649     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
650     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50penCover_003: Set for opening the cover." \,
651     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
652   ),
653   end;
654
655   request(VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_003,
656     START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_060+02:10:00,
657     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
658     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
659     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
660     KEY, "No_Key")
661
662   command(1,
663     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
664     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
        detector,52 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s" \,
665     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,51,30,77,175,5,52,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
666   ),
667   command(2,
668     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
669     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714" \,
670     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode" \,
671     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
672   ),
673   command(3,
674     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:48\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
675     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
676     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
677   ),
678   note(1,
679     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
680     TEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.181 Gibit" \
681   ),
682   command(4,
683     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
684     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
        detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s" \,
685     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM

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686 ),
687   command(5,
688     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
689     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
690     NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
691     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
692   ),
693   command(6,
694     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
695     NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
696     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
697   ),
698   note(2,
699     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
700     TEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.355 Gibit\"\\
701   ),
702   command(7,
703     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
704     NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
705     detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\\,
706     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR_TM
707   ),
708   command(8,
709     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
710     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
711     NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
712     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
713   ),
714   command(9,
715     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
716     NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
717     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
718   ),
719   note(3,
720     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
721     TEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.529 Gibit\"\\
722   ),
723   command(10,
724     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
725     NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
726     detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\\,
727     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR_TM
728   ),
729   command(11,
730     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
731     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
732     NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
733     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
734   ),
735   command(12,
736     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
737     NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
738     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
739   ),
740   note(4,
741     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
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740 TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 0.703 Gibit"\
741 ),
742 command(13,
743 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
744 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
745 detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
746 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
747 ),
748 command(14,
749 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
750 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
751 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
752 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
753 ),
754 command(15,
755 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
756 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
757 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
758 ),
759 note(5,
760 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
761 TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.5 Data Volume in MM 0.877 Gibit"\
762 ),
763 command(16,
764 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
765 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
766 detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
767 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
768 ),
769 command(17,
770 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
771 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
772 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
773 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
774 ),
775 command(18,
776 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
777 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
778 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
779 ),
780 note(6,
781 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
782 TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.6 Data Volume in MM 1.051 Gibit"\
783 ),
784 command(19,
785 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
786 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
787 detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
788 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
789 ),
790 command(20,
791 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
792 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
793 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
794 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
```

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792 ),
793   command(21,
794     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
795     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\\,
796     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
797   ),
798   note(7,
799     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
800     TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.7 Data Volume in MM 1.225 Gibit"\\
801   ),
802   command(22,
803     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
804     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
805     detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\\,
806     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
807   ),
808   command(23,
809     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
810     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\\,
811     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\\,
812     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
813   ),
814   command(24,
815     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
816     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\\,
817     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
818   ),
819   note(8,
820     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
821     TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.8 Data Volume in MM 1.399 Gibit"\\
822   ),
823   command(25,
824     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
825     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
826     detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\\,
827     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
828   ),
829   command(26,
830     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
831     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\\,
832     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\\,
833     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
834   ),
835   command(27,
836     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
837     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\\,
838     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
839   ),
840   note(9,
841     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
842     TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.9 Data Volume in MM 1.573 Gibit"\\
843   ),
844   command(28,
845     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
846     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
847     detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\\,
```

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845     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
846 ),
847     command(29,
848     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
849     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
850     NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
851     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
852 ),
853     command(30,
854     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
855     NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
856     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
857 ),
858     note(10,
859     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
860     TEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.10 Data Volume in MM 1.746 Gibit\"\\
861 ),
862 end;
863
864 request(VIR_VH2_C5CloseCover_003,
865     START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_060+03:09:00,
866     TITLE, "VIR close cover",
867     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
868     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
869     KEY, "No_Key")
870
871 activity(1,
872     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
873     NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C5CloseCover_003: Set for closing the cover.\"\\,
874     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"CLOSE")
875 ),
876 end;
877
878 request(VIR_VH2_C5DumpDataToVR4_003,
879     START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_060+06:28:00,
880     TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",
881     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
882     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
883     KEY, "No_Key")
884
885 command(1,
886     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
887     NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C5DumpDataToVR4_003: begin data dumping into VR4.\"\\,
888     VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
889 ),
890 command(2,
891     SCHEDULED_TIME,\02:39:55\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
892     NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C5DumpDataToVR4_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
893     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
894 ),
895     note(1,
896     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
897     TEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C5DumpDataToVR4_003: data volume in VR4 1.539 Gibit.\"\\
898 ),
899 end;
900
```

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901 request(VIR_VH2_C50openCover_004,  
902     START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_061+02:08:00,  
903     TITLE, "VIR open cover",  
904     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
905     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
906     KEY, "No_Key")  
907  
908     activity(1,  
909         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
910         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50openCover_004: Set for opening the cover."\,  
911         VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")  
912     ),  
913 end;  
914  
915 request(VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_004,  
916     START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_061+02:10:00,  
917     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",  
918     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
919     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
920     KEY, "No_Key")  
921  
922     command(1,  
923         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
924         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_004: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2  
925         detector,52 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,  
926         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,51,30,77,175,5,52,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM  
927     ),  
928     command(2,  
929         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
930         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,  
931         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_004: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,  
932         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")  
933     ),  
934     command(3,  
935         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:48\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
936         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_004: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,  
937         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
938     ),  
939     note(1,  
940         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
941         TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_004: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.181 Gibit"\  
942     ),  
943     command(4,  
944         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
945         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_004: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2  
946         detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,  
947         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM  
948     ),  
949     command(5,  
950         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
951         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,  
952         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_004: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,  
953         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")  
954     ),  
955     command(6,  
956         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
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955     NTEXT, \"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_004: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
956     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
957   ),
958   note(2,
959     SCHEDULED_TIME, \\00:00:05\\, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
960     TEXT, \"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_004: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.355 Gibit\"\\
961   ),
962   command(7,
963     SCHEDULED_TIME, \\00:00:01\\, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
964     NTEXT, \"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_004: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
965     detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\\,
966     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,\"IR_VIS\", \"ALL_SUBFRAMES\", \"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR_TM
967   ),
968   command(8,
969     SCHEDULED_TIME, \\00:00:05\\, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
970     COMMENT, \"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
971     NTEXT, \"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_004: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
972     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
973   ),
974   command(9,
975     SCHEDULED_TIME, \\00:05:36\\, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
976     NTEXT, \"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_004: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
977     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
978   ),
979   note(3,
980     SCHEDULED_TIME, \\00:00:05\\, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
981     TEXT, \"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_004: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.529 Gibit\"\\
982   ),
983   command(10,
984     SCHEDULED_TIME, \\00:00:01\\, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
985     NTEXT, \"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_004: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
986     detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\\,
987     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,\"IR_VIS\", \"ALL_SUBFRAMES\", \"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR_TM
988   ),
989   command(11,
990     SCHEDULED_TIME, \\00:00:05\\, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
991     COMMENT, \"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
992     NTEXT, \"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_004: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
993     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
994   ),
995   command(12,
996     SCHEDULED_TIME, \\00:05:36\\, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
997     NTEXT, \"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_004: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
998     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
999   ),
1000  note(4,
1001    SCHEDULED_TIME, \\00:00:05\\, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1002    TEXT, \"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_004: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 0.703 Gibit\"\\
1003  ),
1004  command(13,
1005    SCHEDULED_TIME, \\00:00:01\\, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1006    NTEXT, \"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_004: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
1007    detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\\,
1008    VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,\"IR_VIS\", \"ALL_SUBFRAMES\", \"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR_TM
1009  ),
1010  command(14,
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1007  command(14,
1008    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1009    COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
1010    NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_004: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
1011    VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
1012  ),
1013  command(15,
1014    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1015    NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_004: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1016    VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1017  ),
1018  note(5,
1019    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1020    TEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_004: Cube N.5 Data Volume in MM 0.877 Gibit\"\\
1021  ),
1022  command(16,
1023    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1024    NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_004: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
1025    detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\\,
1026    VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR_TM
1027  ),
1028  command(17,
1029    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1030    COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
1031    NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_004: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
1032    VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
1033  ),
1034  command(18,
1035    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1036    NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_004: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1037    VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1038  ),
1039  note(6,
1040    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1041    TEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_004: Cube N.6 Data Volume in MM 1.051 Gibit\"\\
1042  ),
1043  command(19,
1044    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1045    NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_004: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
1046    detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\\,
1047    VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR_TM
1048  ),
1049  command(20,
1050    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1051    COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
1052    NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_004: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
1053    VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
1054  ),
1055  command(21,
1056    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1057    NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_004: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1058    VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1059  ),
1060  note(7,
1061    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1062    TEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_004: Cube N.7 Data Volume in MM 1.225 Gibit\"\\
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1061 ),
1062 command(22,
1063   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1064   NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_004: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
   detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
1065   VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1066 ),
1067 command(23,
1068   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1069   COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
1070   NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_004: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1071   VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1072 ),
1073 command(24,
1074   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1075   NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_004: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
1076   VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1077 ),
1078 note(8,
1079   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1080   TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_004: Cube N.8 Data Volume in MM 1.399 Gibit"\
1081 ),
1082 command(25,
1083   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1084   NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_004: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
   detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
1085   VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1086 ),
1087 command(26,
1088   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1089   COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
1090   NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_004: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1091   VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1092 ),
1093 command(27,
1094   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1095   NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_004: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
1096   VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1097 ),
1098 note(9,
1099   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1100   TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_004: Cube N.9 Data Volume in MM 1.573 Gibit"\
1101 ),
1102 command(28,
1103   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1104   NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_004: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
   detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
1105   VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1106 ),
1107 command(29,
1108   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1109   COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
1110   NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_004: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1111   VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1112 ),

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1113   command(30,  
1114     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1115     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_004: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,  
1116     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
1117   ),  
1118   note(10,  
1119     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1120     TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_004: Cube N.10 Data Volume in MM 1.746 Gibit\"\\  
1121   ),  
1122 end;  
1123  
1124 request(VIR_VH2_C5CloseCover_004,  
1125   START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_061+03:09:00,  
1126   TITLE, \"VIR close cover\",  
1127   REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",  
1128   PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",  
1129   KEY, \"No_Key\")  
1130  
1131 activity(1,  
1132   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
1133   NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C5CloseCover_004: Set for closing the cover.\"\\,  
1134   VIR_Cover(vir_cover,\"CLOSE\")  
1135   ),  
1136 end;  
1137  
1138 request(VIR_VH2_C5DumpDataToVR4_004,  
1139   START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_061+06:28:00,  
1140   TITLE, \"VIR dump data into VR4\",  
1141   REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",  
1142   PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",  
1143   KEY, \"No_Key\")  
1144  
1145 command(1,  
1146   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
1147   NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C5DumpDataToVR4_004: begin data dumping into VR4.\"\\,  
1148   VIR_MM_DUMP(\"LOSSLESS\")  
1149   ),  
1150 command(2,  
1151   SCHEDULED_TIME,\02:39:55\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1152   NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C5DumpDataToVR4_004: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,  
1153   VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
1154   ),  
1155   note(1,  
1156     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1157     TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C5DumpDataToVR4_004: data volume in VR4 1.436 Gibit.\"\\  
1158   ),  
1159 end;  
1160  
1161 request(VIR_VH2_C5OpenCover_005,  
1162   START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_062+02:08:00,  
1163   TITLE, \"VIR open cover\",  
1164   REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",  
1165   PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",  
1166   KEY, \"No_Key\")  
1167  
1168 activity(1,  
1169   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
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1170 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_005: Set for opening the cover."\\,
1171 VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
1172 ),
1173 end;
1174
1175 request(VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_005,
1176 START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_062+02:10:00,
1177 TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
1178 REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1179 PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1180 KEY, "No_Key")
1181
1182 command(1,
1183 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1184 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_005: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
detector,52 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\\,
1185 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,51,30,77,175,5,52,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1186 ),
1187 command(2,
1188 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1189 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\\,
1190 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_005: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\\,
1191 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1192 ),
1193 command(3,
1194 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:48\\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1195 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_005: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\\,
1196 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1197 ),
1198 note(1,
1199 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1200 TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_005: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.181 Gibit"\\
1201 ),
1202 command(4,
1203 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1204 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_005: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\\,
1205 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1206 ),
1207 command(5,
1208 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1209 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\\,
1210 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_005: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\\,
1211 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1212 ),
1213 command(6,
1214 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1215 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_005: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\\,
1216 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1217 ),
1218 note(2,
1219 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1220 TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_005: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.355 Gibit"\\
1221 ),
1222 command(7,
1223 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,

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1224 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_005: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
      detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
1225 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1226 ),
1227 command(8,
1228 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1229 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
1230 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_005: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1231 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1232 ),
1233 command(9,
1234 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1235 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_005: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
1236 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1237 ),
1238 note(3,
1239 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1240 TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_005: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.529 Gibit"\
1241 ),
1242 command(10,
1243 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1244 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_005: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
      detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
1245 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1246 ),
1247 command(11,
1248 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1249 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
1250 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_005: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1251 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1252 ),
1253 command(12,
1254 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1255 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_005: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
1256 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1257 ),
1258 note(4,
1259 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1260 TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_005: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 0.703 Gibit"\
1261 ),
1262 command(13,
1263 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1264 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_005: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
      detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
1265 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1266 ),
1267 command(14,
1268 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1269 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
1270 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_005: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1271 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1272 ),
1273 command(15,
1274 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1275 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_005: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",

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1276 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1277 ),
1278 note(5,
1279 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1280 TEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_005: Cube N.5 Data Volume in MM 0.877 Gibit"\
1281 ),
1282 command(16,
1283 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1284 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_005: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
1285 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1286 ),
1287 command(17,
1288 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1289 COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
1290 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_005: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1291 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1292 ),
1293 command(18,
1294 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1295 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_005: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
1296 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1297 ),
1298 note(6,
1299 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1300 TEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_005: Cube N.6 Data Volume in MM 1.051 Gibit"\
1301 ),
1302 command(19,
1303 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1304 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_005: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
1305 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1306 ),
1307 command(20,
1308 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1309 COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
1310 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_005: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1311 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1312 ),
1313 command(21,
1314 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1315 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_005: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
1316 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1317 ),
1318 note(7,
1319 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1320 TEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_005: Cube N.7 Data Volume in MM 1.225 Gibit"\
1321 ),
1322 command(22,
1323 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1324 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_005: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
1325 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1326 ),
1327 command(23,

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1328 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1329 COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
1330 NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_005: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
1331 VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
1332 ),
1333 command(24,
1334 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1335 NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_005: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1336 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1337 ),
1338 note(8,
1339 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1340 TEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_005: Cube N.8 Data Volume in MM 1.399 Gibit\"\\
1341 ),
1342 command(25,
1343 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1344 NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_005: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\\,
1345 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR_TM
1346 ),
1347 command(26,
1348 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1349 COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
1350 NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_005: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
1351 VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
1352 ),
1353 command(27,
1354 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1355 NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_005: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1356 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1357 ),
1358 note(9,
1359 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1360 TEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_005: Cube N.9 Data Volume in MM 1.573 Gibit\"\\
1361 ),
1362 command(28,
1363 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1364 NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_005: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\\,
1365 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR_TM
1366 ),
1367 command(29,
1368 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1369 COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
1370 NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_005: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
1371 VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
1372 ),
1373 command(30,
1374 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1375 NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_005: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1376 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1377 ),
1378 note(10,
1379 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1380 TEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_005: Cube N.10 Data Volume in MM 1.746 Gibit\"\\
1381 ),
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1382 end;
1383
1384 request(VIR_VH2_C5CloseCover_005,
1385   START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_062+03:09:00,
1386   TITLE, "VIR close cover",
1387   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1388   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1389   KEY, "No_Key")
1390
1391 activity(1,
1392   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1393   NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C5CloseCover_005: Set for closing the cover." \,
1394   VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"CLOSE")
1395 ),
1396 end;
1397
1398 request(VIR_VH2_C5DumpDataToVR4_005,
1399   START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_062+06:28:00,
1400   TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",
1401   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1402   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1403   KEY, "No_Key")
1404
1405 command(1,
1406   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1407   NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C5DumpDataToVR4_005: begin data dumping into VR4." \,
1408   VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
1409 ),
1410 command(2,
1411   SCHEDULED_TIME,\02:39:55\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1412   NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C5DumpDataToVR4_005: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
1413   VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1414 ),
1415 note(1,
1416   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1417   TEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C5DumpDataToVR4_005: data volume in VR4 1.338 Gibit." \
1418 ),
1419 end;
1420
1421 request(VIR_VH2_C5OpenCover_006,
1422   START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_063+02:08:00,
1423   TITLE, "VIR open cover",
1424   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1425   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1426   KEY, "No_Key")
1427
1428 activity(1,
1429   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1430   NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C5OpenCover_006: Set for opening the cover." \,
1431   VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
1432 ),
1433 end;
1434
1435 request(VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_006,
1436   START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_063+02:10:00,
1437   TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
1438   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
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1439 PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1440 KEY, "No_Key")
1441
1442 command(1,
1443 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1444 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_006: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
detector,52 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
1445 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,51,30,77,175,5,52,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1446 ),
1447 command(2,
1448 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1449 COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
1450 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_006: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1451 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1452 ),
1453 command(3,
1454 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:48\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1455 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_006: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
1456 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1457 ),
1458 note(1,
1459 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1460 TEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_006: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.181 Gibit"\
1461 ),
1462 command(4,
1463 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1464 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_006: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
1465 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1466 ),
1467 command(5,
1468 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1469 COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
1470 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_006: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1471 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1472 ),
1473 command(6,
1474 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1475 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_006: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
1476 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1477 ),
1478 note(2,
1479 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1480 TEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_006: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.355 Gibit"\
1481 ),
1482 command(7,
1483 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1484 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_006: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
1485 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1486 ),
1487 command(8,
1488 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1489 COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
1490 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_006: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
```

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1491 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1492 ),
1493 command(9,
1494 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1495 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_006: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
1496 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1497 ),
1498 note(3,
1499 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1500 TEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_006: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.529 Gibit" \
1501 ),
1502 command(10,
1503 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1504 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_006: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
1505 detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s" \,
1506 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1507 ),
1508 command(11,
1509 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1510 COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714" \,
1511 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_006: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode" \,
1512 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1513 ),
1514 command(12,
1515 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1516 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_006: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
1517 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1518 ),
1519 note(4,
1520 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1521 TEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_006: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 0.703 Gibit" \
1522 ),
1523 command(13,
1524 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1525 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_006: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
1526 detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s" \,
1527 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1528 ),
1529 command(14,
1530 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1531 COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714" \,
1532 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_006: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode" \,
1533 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1534 ),
1535 command(15,
1536 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1537 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_006: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
1538 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1539 ),
1540 note(5,
1541 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1542 TEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_006: Cube N.5 Data Volume in MM 0.877 Gibit" \
1543 ),
1544 command(16,
1545 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
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1544 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_006: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
      detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
1545 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1546 ),
1547 command(17,
1548 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1549 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
1550 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_006: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1551 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1552 ),
1553 command(18,
1554 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1555 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_006: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
1556 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1557 ),
1558 note(6,
1559 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1560 TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_006: Cube N.6 Data Volume in MM 1.051 Gibit"\
1561 ),
1562 command(19,
1563 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1564 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_006: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
      detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
1565 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1566 ),
1567 command(20,
1568 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1569 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
1570 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_006: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1571 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1572 ),
1573 command(21,
1574 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1575 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_006: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
1576 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1577 ),
1578 note(7,
1579 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1580 TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_006: Cube N.7 Data Volume in MM 1.225 Gibit"\
1581 ),
1582 command(22,
1583 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1584 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_006: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
      detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
1585 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1586 ),
1587 command(23,
1588 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1589 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
1590 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_006: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1591 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1592 ),
1593 command(24,
1594 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1595 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_006: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",

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1596 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1597 ),
1598 note(8,
1599 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1600 TEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_006: Cube N.8 Data Volume in MM 1.399 Gibit"\
1601 ),
1602 command(25,
1603 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1604 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_006: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
1605 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1606 ),
1607 command(26,
1608 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1609 COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
1610 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_006: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1611 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1612 ),
1613 command(27,
1614 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1615 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_006: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
1616 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1617 ),
1618 note(9,
1619 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1620 TEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_006: Cube N.9 Data Volume in MM 1.573 Gibit"\
1621 ),
1622 command(28,
1623 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1624 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_006: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
1625 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1626 ),
1627 command(29,
1628 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1629 COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
1630 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_006: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1631 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1632 ),
1633 command(30,
1634 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1635 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_006: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
1636 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1637 ),
1638 note(10,
1639 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1640 TEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_006: Cube N.10 Data Volume in MM 1.746 Gibit"\
1641 ),
1642 end;
1643
1644 request(VIR_VH2_C5CloseCover_006,
1645 START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_063+03:09:00,
1646 TITLE, "VIR cclose cover",
1647 REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1648 PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1649 KEY, "No_Key")

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1650
1651  activity(1,
1652    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1653    NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C5CloseCover_006: Set for closing the cover.\"\\,
1654    VIR_Cover(vir_cover,\"CLOSE\")
1655  ),
1656 end;
1657
1658 request(VIR_VH2_C5DumpDataToVR4_006,
1659   START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_063+06:28:00,
1660   TITLE, \"VIR dump data into VR4\",
1661   REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
1662   PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
1663   KEY, \"No_Key\")
1664
1665  command(1,
1666    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1667    NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C5DumpDataToVR4_006: begin data dumping into VR4.\"\\,
1668    VIR_MM_DUMP(\"LOSSLESS\")
1669  ),
1670  command(2,
1671    SCHEDULED_TIME,\02:39:55\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1672    NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C5DumpDataToVR4_006: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1673    VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1674  ),
1675  note(1,
1676    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1677    TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C5DumpDataToVR4_006: data volume in VR4 1.279 Gibit.\"\\
1678  ),
1679 end;
1680
1681 request(VIR_VH2_C5OpenCover_007,
1682   START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_064+01:58:00,
1683   TITLE, \"VIR open cover\",
1684   REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
1685   PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
1686   KEY, \"No_Key\")
1687
1688  activity(1,
1689    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1690    NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C5OpenCover_007: Set for opening the cover.\"\\,
1691    VIR_Cover(vir_cover,\"OPEN\")
1692  ),
1693 end;
1694
1695 request(VIR_VH2_C5offNadir4PushBroomToVIR_007,
1696   START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_064+02:00:15,
1697   TITLE, \"VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.\",
1698   REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
1699   PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
1700   KEY, \"No_Key\")
1701
1702  command(1,
1703    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1704    NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C5offNadir4PushBroomToVIR_007: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
1705    detector,52 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\\,
1706    VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",6,51,30,77,175,5,52,\"IR_VIS\", \"ALL_SUBFRAMES\", \"ON\", 10, \"NO_VIR_TM
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1706 ),
1707   command(2,
1708     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1709     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\",\
1710     NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_007: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\",\
1711     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
1712   ),
1713   command(3,
1714     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:48\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1715     NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_007: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\",
1716     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1717   ),
1718   note(1,
1719     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1720     TEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_007: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.181 Gibit\",
1721   ),
1722   command(4,
1723     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1724     NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_007: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
1725     detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\",
1726     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR_TM
1727   ),
1728   command(5,
1729     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1730     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\",\
1731     NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_007: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\",\
1732     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
1733   ),
1734   command(6,
1735     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1736     NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_007: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\",
1737     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1738   ),
1739   note(2,
1740     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1741     TEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_007: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.355 Gibit\",
1742   ),
1743   command(7,
1744     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1745     NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_007: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
1746     detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\",
1747     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR_TM
1748   ),
1749   command(8,
1750     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1751     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\",\
1752     NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_007: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\",\
1753     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
1754   ),
1755   command(9,
1756     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1757     NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_007: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\",
1758     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1759   ),
1760   note(3,
1761     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
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1760 TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_007: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.529 Gibit\"  
1761 ),  
1762 command(10,  
1763 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1764 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_007: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2  
detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\\,  
1765 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR_TM  
1766 ),  
1767 command(11,  
1768 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1769 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,  
1770 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_007: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,  
1771 VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")  
1772 ),  
1773 command(12,  
1774 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1775 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_007: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,  
1776 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
1777 ),  
1778 note(4,  
1779 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1780 TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_007: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 0.703 Gibit\"\\  
1781 ),  
1782 command(13,  
1783 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1784 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_007: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2  
detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\\,  
1785 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR_TM  
1786 ),  
1787 command(14,  
1788 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1789 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,  
1790 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_007: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,  
1791 VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")  
1792 ),  
1793 command(15,  
1794 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1795 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_007: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,  
1796 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
1797 ),  
1798 note(5,  
1799 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1800 TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_007: Cube N.5 Data Volume in MM 0.877 Gibit\"\\  
1801 ),  
1802 command(16,  
1803 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1804 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_007: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2  
detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\\,  
1805 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR_TM  
1806 ),  
1807 command(17,  
1808 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1809 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,  
1810 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_007: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,  
1811 VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
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1812 ),
1813   command(18,
1814     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1815     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_007: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1816     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1817   ),
1818   note(6,
1819     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1820     TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_007: Cube N.6 Data Volume in MM 1.051 Gibit\"\\
1821   ),
1822   command(19,
1823     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1824     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_007: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
1825     detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\\,
1826     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1827   ),
1828   command(20,
1829     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1830     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
1831     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_007: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
1832     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1833   ),
1834   command(21,
1835     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1836     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_007: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1837     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1838   ),
1839   note(7,
1840     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1841     TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_007: Cube N.7 Data Volume in MM 1.225 Gibit\"\\
1842   ),
1843   command(22,
1844     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1845     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_007: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
1846     detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\\,
1847     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1848   ),
1849   command(23,
1850     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1851     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
1852     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_007: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
1853     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1854   ),
1855   command(24,
1856     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1857     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_007: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1858     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1859   ),
1860   note(8,
1861     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1862     TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_007: Cube N.8 Data Volume in MM 1.399 Gibit\"\\
1863   ),
1864   command(25,
1865     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1866     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_007: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
1867     detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\\,
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1865     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1866 ),
1867     command(26,
1868     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1869     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
1870     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_007: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1871     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1872 ),
1873     command(27,
1874     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1875     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_007: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
1876     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1877 ),
1878     note(9,
1879     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1880     TEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_007: Cube N.9 Data Volume in MM 1.573 Gibit"\
1881 ),
1882     command(28,
1883     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1884     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_007: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
1885     detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
1886     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1887 ),
1888     command(29,
1889     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1890     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
1891     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_007: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1892     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1893 ),
1894     command(30,
1895     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1896     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_007: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
1897     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1898 ),
1899     note(10,
1900     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1901     TEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_007: Cube N.10 Data Volume in MM 1.746 Gibit"\
1902 ),
1903 end;
1904 request(VIR_VH2_C5CloseCover_007,
1905     START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_064+03:00:00,
1906     TITLE, "VIR close cover",
1907     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1908     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1909     KEY, "No_Key")
1910
1911 activity(1,
1912     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1913     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C5CloseCover_007: Set for closing the cover."\",
1914     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"CLOSE")
1915 ),
1916 end;
1917
1918 request(VIR_VH2_C5DumpDataToVR4_007,
1919     START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_064+06:28:00,
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1920     TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",
1921     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1922     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1923     KEY, "No_Key")
1924
1925     command(1,
1926         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1927         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C5DumpDataToVR4_007: begin data dumping into VR4." \,
1928         VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
1929     ),
1930     command(2,
1931         SCHEDULED_TIME,\02:39:55\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1932         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C5DumpDataToVR4_007: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
1933         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1934     ),
1935     note(1,
1936         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1937         TEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C5DumpDataToVR4_007: data volume in VR4 1.279 Gibit." \
1938     ),
1939 end;
1940
1941 request(VIR_VH2_C50openCover_008,
1942     START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_065+02:08:00,
1943     TITLE, "VIR open cover",
1944     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1945     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1946     KEY, "No_Key")
1947
1948 activity(1,
1949     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1950     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50openCover_008: Set for opening the cover." \,
1951     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
1952 ),
1953 end;
1954
1955 request(VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_008,
1956     START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_065+02:10:00,
1957     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
1958     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1959     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1960     KEY, "No_Key")
1961
1962     command(1,
1963         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1964         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_008: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
1965         detector,52 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s" \,
1966         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,51,30,77,175,5,52,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1967     ),
1968     command(2,
1969         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1970         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714" \,
1971         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_008: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode" \,
1972         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1973     ),
1974     command(3,
1975         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:48\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1976         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_008: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
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1976 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1977 ),
1978 note(1,
1979 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1980 TEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_008: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.181 Gibit"\
1981 ),
1982 command(4,
1983 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1984 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_008: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
1985 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1986 ),
1987 command(5,
1988 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1989 COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
1990 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_008: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1991 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1992 ),
1993 command(6,
1994 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1995 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_008: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
1996 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1997 ),
1998 note(2,
1999 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2000 TEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_008: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.355 Gibit"\
2001 ),
2002 command(7,
2003 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2004 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_008: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
2005 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
2006 ),
2007 command(8,
2008 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2009 COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
2010 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_008: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
2011 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
2012 ),
2013 command(9,
2014 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2015 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_008: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
2016 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2017 ),
2018 note(3,
2019 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2020 TEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_008: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.529 Gibit"\
2021 ),
2022 command(10,
2023 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2024 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_008: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
2025 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
2026 ),
2027 command(11,

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2028 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2029 COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
2030 NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_008: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
2031 VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
2032 ),
2033 command(12,
2034 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2035 NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_008: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
2036 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2037 ),
2038 note(4,
2039 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2040 TEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_008: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 0.703 Gibit\"\\
2041 ),
2042 command(13,
2043 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2044 NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_008: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\\,
2045 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR_TM
2046 ),
2047 command(14,
2048 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2049 COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
2050 NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_008: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
2051 VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
2052 ),
2053 command(15,
2054 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2055 NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_008: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
2056 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2057 ),
2058 note(5,
2059 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2060 TEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_008: Cube N.5 Data Volume in MM 0.877 Gibit\"\\
2061 ),
2062 command(16,
2063 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2064 NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_008: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\\,
2065 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR_TM
2066 ),
2067 command(17,
2068 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2069 COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
2070 NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_008: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
2071 VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
2072 ),
2073 command(18,
2074 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2075 NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_008: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
2076 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2077 ),
2078 note(6,
2079 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2080 TEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_008: Cube N.6 Data Volume in MM 1.051 Gibit\"\\
2081 ),
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2082  command(19,
2083    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2084    NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_008: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
2085    detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
2086    VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
2087  ),
2088  command(20,
2089    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2090    COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
2091    NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_008: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
2092    VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
2093  ),
2094  command(21,
2095    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2096    NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_008: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
2097    VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2098  ),
2099  note(7,
2100    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2101    TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_008: Cube N.7 Data Volume in MM 1.225 Gibit"\
2102  ),
2103  command(22,
2104    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2105    NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_008: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
2106    detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
2107    VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
2108  ),
2109  command(23,
2110    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2111    COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
2112    NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_008: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
2113    VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
2114  ),
2115  command(24,
2116    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2117    NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_008: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
2118    VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2119  ),
2120  note(8,
2121    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2122    TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_008: Cube N.8 Data Volume in MM 1.399 Gibit"\
2123  ),
2124  command(25,
2125    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2126    NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_008: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
2127    detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
2128    VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
2129  ),
2130  command(26,
2131    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2132    COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
2133    NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_008: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
2134    VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
2135  ),
2136  command(27,

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2134     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2135     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_008: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\\,
2136     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2137 ),
2138     note(9,
2139     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2140     TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_008: Cube N.9 Data Volume in MM 1.573 Gibit"\\
2141     ),
2142     command(28,
2143     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2144     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_008: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
2145     detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\\,
2146     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
2147     ),
2148     command(29,
2149     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2150     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\\,
2151     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_008: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\\,
2152     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
2153     ),
2154     command(30,
2155     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2156     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_008: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\\,
2157     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2158     ),
2159     note(10,
2160     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2161     TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_008: Cube N.10 Data Volume in MM 1.746 Gibit"\\
2162     ),
2163     end;
2164     request(VIR_VH2_C5closeCover_008,
2165     START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_065+03:09:00,
2166     TITLE, "VIR close cover",
2167     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
2168     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
2169     KEY, "No_Key")
2170
2171     activity(1,
2172     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
2173     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C5closeCover_008: Set for closing the cover."\\,
2174     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"CLOSE")
2175     ),
2176     end;
2177
2178     request(VIR_VH2_C5DumpDataToVR4_008,
2179     START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_065+06:28:00,
2180     TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",
2181     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
2182     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
2183     KEY, "No_Key")
2184
2185     command(1,
2186     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
2187     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C5DumpDataToVR4_008: begin data dumping into VR4."\\,
2188     VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
2189     ),
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2190  command(2,
2191    SCHEDULED_TIME,\02:39:55\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2192    NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C5DumpDataToVR4_008: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\\,
2193    VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2194  ),
2195  note(1,
2196    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2197    TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C5DumpDataToVR4_008: data volume in VR4 1.279 Gibit."\\
2198  ),
2199  end;
2200
2201  request(VIR_VH2_C5openCover_009,
2202    START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_066+02:28:00,
2203    TITLE, "VIR open cover",
2204    REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
2205    PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
2206    KEY, "No_Key")
2207
2208  activity(1,
2209    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
2210    NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C5openCover_009: Set for opening the cover."\\,
2211    VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
2212  ),
2213  end;
2214
2215  request(VIR_VH2_C5offNadir4PushBroomToVIR_009,
2216    START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_066+02:30:00,
2217    TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
2218    REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
2219    PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
2220    KEY, "No_Key")
2221
2222  command(1,
2223    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
2224    NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C5offNadir4PushBroomToVIR_009: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
2225    detector,52 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\\,
2226    VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,51,30,77,175,5,52,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
2227  ),
2228  command(2,
2229    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2230    COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\\,
2231    NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C5offNadir4PushBroomToVIR_009: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\\,
2232    VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
2233  ),
2234  command(3,
2235    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:48\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2236    NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C5offNadir4PushBroomToVIR_009: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\\,
2237    VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2238  ),
2239  note(1,
2240    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2241    TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C5offNadir4PushBroomToVIR_009: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.181 Gibit"\\
2242  ),
2243  command(4,
2244    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2245    NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C5offNadir4PushBroomToVIR_009: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
2246    detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\\,
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2245     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
2246 ),
2247     command(5,
2248     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2249     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
2250     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_009: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
2251     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
2252 ),
2253     command(6,
2254     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2255     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_009: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
2256     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2257 ),
2258     note(2,
2259     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2260     TEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_009: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.355 Gibit"\
2261 ),
2262     command(7,
2263     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2264     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_009: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
2265     detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
2266     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
2267 ),
2268     command(8,
2269     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2270     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
2271     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_009: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
2272     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
2273 ),
2274     command(9,
2275     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2276     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_009: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
2277     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2278 ),
2279     note(3,
2280     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2281     TEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_009: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.529 Gibit"\
2282 ),
2283     command(10,
2284     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2285     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_009: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
2286     detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
2287     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
2288 ),
2289     command(11,
2290     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2291     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
2292     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_009: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
2293     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
2294 ),
2295     command(12,
2296     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2297     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_009: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
2298     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2299 ),
```

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2298 note(4,
2299   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2300   TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_009: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 0.703 Gibit"\
2301 ),
2302 command(13,
2303   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2304   NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_009: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
   detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
2305   VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
2306 ),
2307 command(14,
2308   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2309   COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
2310   NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_009: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
2311   VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
2312 ),
2313 command(15,
2314   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2315   NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_009: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
2316   VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2317 ),
2318 note(5,
2319   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2320   TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_009: Cube N.5 Data Volume in MM 0.877 Gibit"\
2321 ),
2322 command(16,
2323   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2324   NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_009: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
   detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
2325   VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
2326 ),
2327 command(17,
2328   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2329   COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
2330   NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_009: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
2331   VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
2332 ),
2333 command(18,
2334   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2335   NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_009: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
2336   VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2337 ),
2338 note(6,
2339   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2340   TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_009: Cube N.6 Data Volume in MM 1.051 Gibit"\
2341 ),
2342 command(19,
2343   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2344   NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_009: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
   detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
2345   VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
2346 ),
2347 command(20,
2348   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2349   COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
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2350 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_009: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
2351 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
2352 ),
2353 command(21,
2354 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2355 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_009: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
2356 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2357 ),
2358 note(7,
2359 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2360 TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_009: Cube N.7 Data Volume in MM 1.225 Gibit"\
2361 ),
2362 command(22,
2363 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2364 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_009: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
2365 detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
2366 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
2367 ),
2368 command(23,
2369 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2370 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
2371 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_009: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
2372 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
2373 ),
2374 command(24,
2375 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2376 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_009: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
2377 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2378 ),
2379 note(8,
2380 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2381 TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_009: Cube N.8 Data Volume in MM 1.399 Gibit"\
2382 ),
2383 command(25,
2384 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2385 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_009: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
2386 detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
2387 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
2388 ),
2389 command(26,
2390 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2391 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
2392 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_009: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
2393 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
2394 ),
2395 command(27,
2396 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2397 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_009: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
2398 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2399 ),
2400 note(9,
2401 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2402 TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_009: Cube N.9 Data Volume in MM 1.573 Gibit"\
2403 ),
2404 command(28,
2405 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,

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2404 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_009: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
2405 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","0N",10,"NO_VIR_TM
2406 ),
2407 command(29,
2408 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2409 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
2410 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_009: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
2411 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
2412 ),
2413 command(30,
2414 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2415 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_009: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
2416 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2417 ),
2418 note(10,
2419 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2420 TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_009: Cube N.10 Data Volume in MM 1.746 Gibit"\
2421 ),
2422 end;
2423
2424 request(VIR_VH2_C5CloseCover_009,
2425 START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_066+03:30:00,
2426 TITLE, "VIR close cover",
2427 REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
2428 PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
2429 KEY, "No_Key")
2430
2431 activity(1,
2432 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
2433 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C5CloseCover_009: Set for closing the cover."\",
2434 VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"CLOSE")
2435 ),
2436 end;
2437
2438 request(VIR_VH2_C5DumpDataToVR4_009,
2439 START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_066+06:28:00,
2440 TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",
2441 REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
2442 PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
2443 KEY, "No_Key")
2444
2445 command(1,
2446 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
2447 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C5DumpDataToVR4_009: begin data dumping into VR4."\",
2448 VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
2449 ),
2450 command(2,
2451 SCHEDULED_TIME,\02:39:55\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2452 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C5DumpDataToVR4_009: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
2453 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2454 ),
2455 note(1,
2456 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2457 TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C5DumpDataToVR4_009: data volume in VR4 1.279 Gibit."\"
2458 ),
2459 end;
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2460
2461 request(VIR_VH2_C50openCover_010,
2462     START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_067+02:08:00,
2463     TITLE, "VIR open cover",
2464     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
2465     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
2466     KEY, "No_Key")
2467
2468 activity(1,
2469     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
2470     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50openCover_010: Set for opening the cover." \,
2471     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
2472 ),
2473 end;
2474
2475 request(VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_010,
2476     START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_067+02:10:00,
2477     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
2478     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
2479     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
2480     KEY, "No_Key")
2481
2482 command(1,
2483     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
2484     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_010: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
2485     detector,52 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s" \,
2486     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,51,30,77,175,5,52,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
2487 ),
2488 command(2,
2489     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2490     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714" \,
2491     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_010: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode" \,
2492     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
2493 ),
2494 command(3,
2495     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:48\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2496     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_010: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
2497     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2498 ),
2499 note(1,
2500     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2501     TEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_010: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.181 Gibit" \
2502 ),
2503 command(4,
2504     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2505     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_010: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
2506     detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s" \,
2507     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
2508 ),
2509 command(5,
2510     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2511     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714" \,
2512     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_010: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode" \,
2513     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
2514 ),
2515 command(6,
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2514     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2515     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_010: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\\,
2516     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2517   ),
2518   note(2,
2519     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2520     TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_010: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.355 Gibit"\\
2521   ),
2522   command(7,
2523     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2524     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_010: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
2525     detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\\,
2526     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
2527   ),
2528   command(8,
2529     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2530     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\\,
2531     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_010: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\\,
2532     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
2533   ),
2534   command(9,
2535     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2536     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_010: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\\,
2537     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2538   ),
2539   note(3,
2540     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2541     TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_010: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.529 Gibit"\\
2542   ),
2543   command(10,
2544     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2545     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_010: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
2546     detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\\,
2547     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
2548   ),
2549   command(11,
2550     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2551     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\\,
2552     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_010: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\\,
2553     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
2554   ),
2555   command(12,
2556     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2557     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_010: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\\,
2558     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2559   ),
2560   note(4,
2561     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2562     TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_010: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 0.703 Gibit"\\
2563   ),
2564   command(13,
2565     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2566     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_010: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
2567     detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\\,
2568     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
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2566 ),
2567   command(14,
2568     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2569     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
2570     NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_010: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
2571     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
2572   ),
2573   command(15,
2574     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2575     NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_010: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
2576     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2577   ),
2578   note(5,
2579     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2580     TEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_010: Cube N.5 Data Volume in MM 0.877 Gibit\"\\
2581   ),
2582   command(16,
2583     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2584     NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_010: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
2585     detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\\,
2586     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR_TM
2587   ),
2588   command(17,
2589     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2590     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
2591     NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_010: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
2592     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
2593   ),
2594   command(18,
2595     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2596     NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_010: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
2597     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2598   ),
2599   note(6,
2600     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2601     TEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_010: Cube N.6 Data Volume in MM 1.051 Gibit\"\\
2602   ),
2603   command(19,
2604     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2605     NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_010: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
2606     detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\\,
2607     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR_TM
2608   ),
2609   command(20,
2610     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2611     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
2612     NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_010: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
2613     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
2614   ),
2615   command(21,
2616     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2617     NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_010: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
2618     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2619   ),
2620   note(7,
2621     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
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2620 TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_010: Cube N.7 Data Volume in MM 1.225 Gibit"\
2621 ),
2622 command(22,
2623 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2624 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_010: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
2625 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
2626 ),
2627 command(23,
2628 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2629 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
2630 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_010: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
2631 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
2632 ),
2633 command(24,
2634 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2635 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_010: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
2636 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2637 ),
2638 note(8,
2639 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2640 TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_010: Cube N.8 Data Volume in MM 1.399 Gibit"\
2641 ),
2642 command(25,
2643 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2644 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_010: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
2645 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
2646 ),
2647 command(26,
2648 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2649 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
2650 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_010: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
2651 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
2652 ),
2653 command(27,
2654 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2655 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_010: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
2656 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2657 ),
2658 note(9,
2659 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2660 TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_010: Cube N.9 Data Volume in MM 1.573 Gibit"\
2661 ),
2662 command(28,
2663 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2664 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_010: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2
detector,50 frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
2665 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
2666 ),
2667 command(29,
2668 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2669 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
2670 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_010: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
2671 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
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```
2672 ),
2673   command(30,
2674     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2675     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_010: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
2676     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2677   ),
2678   note(10,
2679     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2680     TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C50ffNadir4PushBroomToVIR_010: Cube N.10 Data Volume in MM 1.746 Gibit\"\\
2681   ),
2682 end;
2683
2684 request(VIR_VH2_C5CloseCover_010,
2685   START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_067+03:09:00,
2686   TITLE, \"VIR cclose cover\",
2687   REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
2688   PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
2689   KEY, \"No_Key\")
2690
2691 activity(1,
2692   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
2693   NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C5CloseCover_010: Set for closing the cover.\"\\,
2694   VIR_Cover(vir_cover,\"CLOSE\")
2695 ),
2696 end;
2697
2698 request(VIR_VH2_C5DumpDataToVR4_010,
2699   START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_067+06:28:00,
2700   TITLE, \"VIR dump data into VR4\",
2701   REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
2702   PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
2703   KEY, \"No_Key\")
2704
2705 command(1,
2706   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
2707   NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C5DumpDataToVR4_010: begin data dumping into VR4.\"\\,
2708   VIR_MM_DUMP(\"LOSSLESS\")
2709 ),
2710 command(2,
2711   SCHEDULED_TIME,\02:39:55\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2712   NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C5DumpDataToVR4_010: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
2713   VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2714 ),
2715   note(1,
2716     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2717     TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C5DumpDataToVR4_010: data volume in VR4 1.279 Gibit.\"\\
2718   ),
2719 end;
2720
2721 request(VIR_VH2_VMLEND_C5HAMO2,
2722   START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_067+09:09:00,
2723   TITLE, \"VIR Sequence End - vir_vh2_C5HAMO2 (ds120)\",
2724   REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
2725   PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
2726   KEY, \"No_Key\")
2727
2728 note(1,
```

```

2729     SCHEDULED_TIME, \00:00:00\, FROM_REQUEST_START,
2730     TEXT, \ "End sequence ds120 - vir_vh2_C5HAMO2" \
2731     ),
2732 end;
2733
2734 $$EOF

```

The following SASF files were processed:

4.2 The sequence: vir_vh2_C6HAMO2.r04.sasf

Line	Code	File
1	CCSD3ZF000010000000INJPL3KS0L015\$MARK\$;	sasf
2	MISSION_NAME = DAWN;	
3	SPACECRAFT_NAME = DAWN;	
4	DATA_SET_ID = SPACECRAFT_ACTIVITY_SEQUENCE_DSC;	
5	FILE_NAME = vir_vh2_C6HAMO2.r04.sasf;	
6	APPLICABLE_START_TIME = 2012-201T16:56:47.000;	
7	APPLICABLE_STOP_TIME = 2012-208T00:00:00.000;	
8	PRODUCT_CREATION_TIME = 2012-163T05:55:32.000;	
9	PRODUCER_ID = SEQ;	
10	SEQ_ID = vir_vh2_C6HAMO2.r04;	
11	HOST_ID = dawnjpldsc;	
12	CCSD3RE00000\$MARK\$NJPL3IF0M01300000001;	
13	\$\$DWN SPACECRAFT ACTIVITY SEQUENCE FILE	
14	*****	
15	*PROJECT DWN	
16	*SPACECRAFT 203	
17	*OPERATOR DWNDSC team account	
18	*FILE_CMPLT TRUE	
19	*DATE Mon Jun 11 05:55:32 2012	
20	*seqgenCore V32.0 Tue Dec 14 17:21:23 PST 2010	
21	*BEGIN 2012-201T16:56:47.000	
22	*CUTOFF 2012-208T00:00:00.000	
23	*TITLE VIR_VH2_da030_Cycle_6_ds122	
24	*EPOCHS_DEF	
25	*EPOCHS_END	
26	*Input files used:	
27	*File Type Last modified File name	
28	*SC_MODEL Tue Apr 10 18:57:18 2012 /delivery/MSOP/J6.7.1-DAWN/seq/smf/dawn.cd1.FDAWN_9_0DDAWN_9_0_0_2012Apr10_11_56_00.smf	
29	*CATALOG Wed Mar 14 19:26:38 2012 /delivery/MSOP/J6.7.1-DAWN/seq/satf/dawn.cd1.FDAWN_9_0DDAWN_9_0_0_2012Mar14_1200_1.satf	
30	*LEGENDS Tue May 11 21:36:07 1999 /delivery/MSOP/J6.7.1-DAWN/seq/legend/Dawn.1.0.legend	
31	*CATALOG Thu Mar 24 16:44:44 2011 /delivery/MSOP/J6.7.1-DAWN/seq/satf/dawn.blk.d_fb20_eng_blib_mod.900.r4.satf	
32	*CATALOG Thu May 20 15:12:56 2010 /delivery/MSOP/J6.7.1-DAWN/seq/satf/dawn.blk.d_fb19_sci_blib_mod.900.r3.satf	
33	*CATALOG Thu May 20 15:12:39 2010 /delivery/MSOP/J6.7.1-DAWN/seq/satf/dawn.blk.d_fb17_safe_blib_mod.900.r2.satf	
34	*CONTEXT Thu May 24 20:41:12 2007 /delivery/MSOP/J6.7.1-DAWN/seq/cvf/dawn.sct.cvf	
35	*CONTEXT Wed Mar 14 17:36:14 2012 /delivery/MSOP/J6.7.1-DAWN/seq/cvf/dawn.cvf	
36	*CONTEXT Mon Mar 12 17:15:57 2007 /delivery/MSOP/J6.7.1-DAWN/seq/cvf/msop.soe.cvf	
37	*CONTEXT Mon Apr 21 19:28:05 2003 /delivery/MSOPRW/J6.7.1-DAWN/seq_rw/seq_config/dsn_config/msop.dsn.cvf	
38	*CONTEXT Thu Aug 4 18:09:05 2011 /delivery/MSOPRW/J6.7.1-DAWN/seq_rw/seq_config/dsn_config/soe_defaults_203.cvf	
39	*CONTEXT Thu Aug 2 15:59:05 2007 /delivery/MSOPRW/J6.7.1-DAWN/seq_rw/seq_config/dsn_config/dsn_config.cvf	

```
40 *CONTEXT Thu Jun 7 18:59:41 2012 /export/home/dwndsc/dsc/sequencing/vesta/vh2/  
optg_vesta_DA029_DA030_v1.cvf  
41 *CLOCK Thu Apr 26 16:26:35 2012 /delivery/MSOPRW/J6.7.1-DAWN/seq_rw/seq_input/sclk/  
DAWN_203_PSCLKSCET.00003  
42 *SEQUENCE Mon Jun 11 05:55:32 2012 /export/home/dwndsc/dsc/sequencing/vesta/vh2/da030/vir/r04/  
vir_vh2_C6HAMO2.r04.sasf  
43 *ALLOCATION  
44 *BG_SEQUENCE  
45 *CAT_NO_VML  
46 *CONDITIONS  
47 *DEFINITION  
48 *DEP_CONTEXT  
49 *EVENTS  
50 *LIGHTTIME  
51 *MASK  
52 *OPTG_FD  
53 *GEOMETRY  
54 *REDUNDANT  
55 *REQUESTS  
56 *RESOLUTION  
57 *RULES  
58 *SCRIPT  
59 *ON_BOARD_SE  
60 *TELEMETRY  
61 *TYPEDEF  
62 *VIEWPERIOD  
63 *VIEW_FD  
64 *****  
65 $$E0H  
66 $$E0D  
67 request(VIR_VH2_VMLSTART_C6HAMO2,  
68 START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_068+00:44:00,  
69 TITLE, "VIR Sequence Start - vir_vh2_C6HAMO2 (ds122)",  
70 REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
71 PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
72 KEY, "No_Key")  
73  
74 activity(1,  
75 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
76 SEQTRAN_directive(VML_START,2000-001T00:00:00.000,2050-001T00:00:00.000,"ABSLTE","vir_vh2_C6HAMO2","v  
fb05")  
77 ),  
78 note(1,  
79 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
80 TEXT,\ "Begin sequence ds122 - vir_vh2_C6HAMO2"\  
81 ),  
82 end;  
83  
84 request(VIR_VH2_C60openCover_001,  
85 START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_068+00:45:00,  
86 TITLE, "VIR open cover",  
87 REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
88 PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
89 KEY, "No_Key")  
90  
91 activity(1,  
92 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
```

```
93     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6openCover_001: Set for opening the cover."\\,
94     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
95   ),
96   end;
97
98   request(VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_001,
99     START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_068+00:47:00,
100    TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
101    REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
102    PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
103    KEY, "No_Key")
104
105   command(1,
106     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
107     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
108     frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\\,
109     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
110   ),
111   command(2,
112     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
113     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\\,
114     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\\,
115     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
116   ),
117   command(3,
118     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
119     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\\,
120     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
121   ),
122   note(1,
123     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
124     TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.174 Gibit"\\
125   ),
126   command(4,
127     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
128     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
129     frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\\,
130     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
131   ),
132   command(5,
133     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
134     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\\,
135     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\\,
136     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
137   ),
138   command(6,
139     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
140     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\\,
141     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
142   ),
143   note(2,
144     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
145     TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.348 Gibit"\\
146   ),
147   command(7,
148     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
```

```
147 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
148 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
149 ),
150 command(8,
151 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
152 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
153 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
154 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
155 ),
156 command(9,
157 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
158 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
159 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
160 ),
161 note(3,
162 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
163 TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.522 Gibit"\
164 ),
165 command(10,
166 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
167 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
168 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
169 ),
170 command(11,
171 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
172 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
173 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
174 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
175 ),
176 command(12,
177 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
178 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
179 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
180 ),
181 note(4,
182 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
183 TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 0.696 Gibit"\
184 ),
185 command(13,
186 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
187 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
188 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
189 ),
190 command(14,
191 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
192 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
193 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
194 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
195 ),
196 command(15,
197 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
198 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
```

```
199     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
200   ),
201   note(5,
202     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
203     TEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.5 Data Volume in MM 0.870 Gibit"\
204   ),
205   end;
206
207   request(VIR_VH2_C6CloseCover_001,
208     START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_068+01:33:00,
209     TITLE, "VIR close cover",
210     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
211     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
212     KEY, "No_Key")
213
214   activity(1,
215     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
216     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C6CloseCover_001: Set for closing the cover."\,
217     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"CLOSE")
218   ),
219   end;
220
221   request(VIR_VH2_C6DumpDataToVR4_001,
222     START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_068+01:35:00,
223     TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",
224     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
225     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
226     KEY, "No_Key")
227
228   command(1,
229     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
230     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C6DumpDataToVR4_001: begin data dumping into VR4."\,
231     VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
232   ),
233   command(2,
234     SCHEDULED_TIME,\01:59:55\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
235     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C6DumpDataToVR4_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
236     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
237   ),
238   note(1,
239     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
240     TEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C6DumpDataToVR4_001: data volume in VR4 0.637 Gibit."\
241   ),
242   end;
243
244   request(VIR_VH2_C6FullCalibNoCooling_001,
245     START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_068+11:25:29,
246     TITLE, "VIR full calibration sequence",
247     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
248     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
249     KEY, "No_Key")
250
251   command(1,
252     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
253     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C6FullCalibNoCooling_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY"\,
254     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
255   ),
```

```
256   command(2,  
257     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
258     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6FullCalibNoCooling_001: perform the internal full calibration"\,  
259     VIR_CALIBRATION("H_SPE_H_SPA_F","CLOSECOVERATEND","FULLCALSEQ")  
260   ),  
261   command(3,  
262     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:15:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
263     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6FullCalibNoCooling_001: begin data dumping into VR4."\  
264     VIR_MM_DUMP("NO_COMPRESSION")  
265   ),  
266   command(4,  
267     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:15:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
268     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6FullCalibNoCooling_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY"\,  
269     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
270   ),  
271   note(1,  
272     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
273     TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6FullCalibNoCooling_001: full calibration is finished."\  
274   ),  
275   note(2,  
276     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
277     TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6FullCalibNoCooling_001: Data Volume in VR4: 0.126 Gibit,120 pages, 15960  
278     packets."\  
279   end;  
280  
281   request(VIR_VH2_C6OpenCover_002,  
282     START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_069+00:45:00,  
283     TITLE, "VIR open cover",  
284     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
285     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
286     KEY, "No_Key")  
287  
288   activity(1,  
289     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
290     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6OpenCover_002: Set for opening the cover."\  
291     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")  
292   ),  
293   end;  
294  
295   request(VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_002,  
296     START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_069+00:47:00,  
297     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",  
298     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
299     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
300     KEY, "No_Key")  
301  
302   command(1,  
303     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
304     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_002: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50  
305     frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\  
306     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM  
307   ),  
308   command(2,  
309     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
310     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\  
311     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_002: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\  

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```
311 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
312 ),
313 command(3,
314 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
315 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\ ,
316 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
317 ),
318 note(1,
319 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
320 TEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_002: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.174 Gibit"\
321 ),
322 command(4,
323 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
324 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_002: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\ ,
325 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
326 ),
327 command(5,
328 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
329 COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\ ,
330 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_002: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\ ,
331 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
332 ),
333 command(6,
334 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
335 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\ ,
336 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
337 ),
338 note(2,
339 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
340 TEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_002: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.348 Gibit"\
341 ),
342 command(7,
343 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
344 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_002: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\ ,
345 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
346 ),
347 command(8,
348 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
349 COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\ ,
350 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_002: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\ ,
351 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
352 ),
353 command(9,
354 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
355 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\ ,
356 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
357 ),
358 note(3,
359 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
360 TEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_002: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.522 Gibit"\
361 ),
362 command(10,
363 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
```

```
364 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_002: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
365 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
366 ),
367 command(11,
368 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
369 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
370 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_002: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
371 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
372 ),
373 command(12,
374 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
375 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
376 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
377 ),
378 note(4,
379 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
380 TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_002: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 0.696 Gibit"\
381 ),
382 command(13,
383 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
384 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_002: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
385 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
386 ),
387 command(14,
388 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
389 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
390 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_002: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
391 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
392 ),
393 command(15,
394 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
395 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
396 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
397 ),
398 note(5,
399 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
400 TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_002: Cube N.5 Data Volume in MM 0.870 Gibit"\
401 ),
402 end;
403
404 request(VIR_VH2_C6CloseCover_002,
405 START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_069+01:33:00,
406 TITLE, "VIR close cover",
407 REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
408 PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
409 KEY, "No_Key")
410
411 activity(1,
412 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
413 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6CloseCover_002: Set for closing the cover."\",
414 VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"CLOSE")
415 ),
416 end;
417
```

```
418 request(VIR_VH2_C6DumpDataToVR4_002,  
419     START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_069+01:35:00,  
420     TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",  
421     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
422     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
423     KEY, "No_Key")  
424  
425     command(1,  
426         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
427         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6DumpDataToVR4_002: begin data dumping into VR4."\  
428         VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")  
429     ),  
430     command(2,  
431         SCHEDULED_TIME,\01:59:55\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
432         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6DumpDataToVR4_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\  
433         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
434     ),  
435     note(1,  
436         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
437         TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6DumpDataToVR4_002: data volume in VR4 0.763 Gibit."\  
438     ),  
439     end;  
440  
441 request(VIR_VH2_C60penCover_003,  
442     START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_070+00:45:00,  
443     TITLE, "VIR open cover",  
444     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
445     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
446     KEY, "No_Key")  
447  
448     activity(1,  
449         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
450         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C60penCover_003: Set for opening the cover."\  
451         VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")  
452     ),  
453     end;  
454  
455 request(VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_003,  
456     START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_070+00:47:00,  
457     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",  
458     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
459     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
460     KEY, "No_Key")  
461  
462     command(1,  
463         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
464         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50  
465         frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\  
466         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM  
467     ),  
468     command(2,  
469         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
470         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\  
471         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\  
472         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")  
473     ),  
474     command(3,
```

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474     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
475     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,  
476     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
477   ),  
478   note(1,  
479     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
480     TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.174 Gibit\"\\  
481   ),  
482   command(4,  
483     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
484     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50  
         frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\\,  
485     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM  
486   ),  
487   command(5,  
488     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
489     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,  
490     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,  
491     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")  
492   ),  
493   command(6,  
494     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
495     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,  
496     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
497   ),  
498   note(2,  
499     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
500     TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.348 Gibit\"\\  
501   ),  
502   command(7,  
503     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
504     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50  
         frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\\,  
505     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM  
506   ),  
507   command(8,  
508     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
509     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,  
510     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,  
511     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")  
512   ),  
513   command(9,  
514     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
515     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,  
516     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
517   ),  
518   note(3,  
519     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
520     TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.522 Gibit\"\\  
521   ),  
522   command(10,  
523     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
524     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50  
         frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\\,  
525     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
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526 ),
527   command(11,
528     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
529     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
530     NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
531     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
532   ),
533   command(12,
534     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
535     NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
536     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
537   ),
538   note(4,
539     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
540     TEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 0.696 Gibit\"\\
541   ),
542   command(13,
543     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
544     NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
545     frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\\,
546     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR_TM
547   ),
548     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
549     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
550     NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
551     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
552   ),
553   command(15,
554     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
555     NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
556     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
557   ),
558   note(5,
559     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
560     TEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.5 Data Volume in MM 0.870 Gibit\"\\
561   ),
562 end;
563
564 request(VIR_VH2_C6CloseCover_003,
565   START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_070+01:33:00,
566   TITLE, \"VIR cclose cover\",
567   REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
568   PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
569   KEY, \"No_Key\")
570
571 activity(1,
572   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
573   NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C6CloseCover_003: Set for closing the cover.\"\\,
574   VIR_Cover(vir_cover,\"CLOSE\")
575 ),
576 end;
577
578 request(VIR_VH2_C6DumpDataToVR4_003,
579   START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_070+01:35:00,
580   TITLE, \"VIR dump data into VR4\",
581   REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
```

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582     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
583     KEY, "No_Key")
584
585     command(1,
586     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
587     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C6DumpDataToVR4_003: begin data dumping into VR4." \,
588     VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
589     ),
590     command(2,
591     SCHEDULED_TIME,\01:59:55\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
592     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C6DumpDataToVR4_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
593     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
594     ),
595     note(1,
596     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
597     TEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C6DumpDataToVR4_003: data volume in VR4 0.704 Gibit." \
598     ),
599     end;
600
601     request(VIR_VH2_C6openCover_004,
602     START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_071+00:45:00,
603     TITLE, "VIR open cover",
604     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
605     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
606     KEY, "No_Key")
607
608     activity(1,
609     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
610     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C6openCover_004: Set for opening the cover." \,
611     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
612     ),
613     end;
614
615     request(VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_004,
616     START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_071+00:47:00,
617     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
618     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
619     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
620     KEY, "No_Key")
621
622     command(1,
623     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
624     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_004: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s" \,
625     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
626     ),
627     command(2,
628     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
629     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714" \,
630     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_004: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode" \,
631     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
632     ),
633     command(3,
634     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
635     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_004: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
636     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
637     ),

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638 note(1,
639   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
640   TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_004: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.174 Gibit"\
641 ),
642 command(4,
643   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
644   NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_004: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
   frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
645   VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
646 ),
647 command(5,
648   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
649   COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
650   NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_004: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
651   VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
652 ),
653 command(6,
654   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
655   NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_004: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
656   VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
657 ),
658 note(2,
659   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
660   TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_004: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.348 Gibit"\
661 ),
662 command(7,
663   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
664   NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_004: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
   frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
665   VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
666 ),
667 command(8,
668   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
669   COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
670   NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_004: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
671   VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
672 ),
673 command(9,
674   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
675   NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_004: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
676   VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
677 ),
678 note(3,
679   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
680   TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_004: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.522 Gibit"\
681 ),
682 command(10,
683   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
684   NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_004: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
   frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
685   VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
686 ),
687 command(11,
688   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
689   COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
```

```
690 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_004: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,  
691 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")  
692 ),  
693 command(12,  
694 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
695 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_004: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\  
696 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
697 ),  
698 note(4,  
699 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
700 TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_004: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 0.696 Gibit"\  
701 ),  
702 command(13,  
703 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
704 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_004: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50  
frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,  
705 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM  
706 ),  
707 command(14,  
708 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
709 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,  
710 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_004: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,  
711 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")  
712 ),  
713 command(15,  
714 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
715 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_004: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\  
716 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
717 ),  
718 note(5,  
719 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
720 TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_004: Cube N.5 Data Volume in MM 0.870 Gibit"\  
721 ),  
722 end;  
723  
724 request(VIR_VH2_C6CloseCover_004,  
725 START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_071+01:33:00,  
726 TITLE, "VIR cclose cover",  
727 REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
728 PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
729 KEY, "No_Key")  
730  
731 activity(1,  
732 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
733 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6CloseCover_004: Set for closing the cover."\  
734 VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"CLOSE")  
735 ),  
736 end;  
737  
738 request(VIR_VH2_C6DumpDataToVR4_004,  
739 START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_071+01:35:00,  
740 TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",  
741 REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
742 PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
743 KEY, "No_Key")  
744  
745 command(1,
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746     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
747     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6DumpDataToVR4_004: begin data dumping into VR4.\"",
748     VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
749 ),
750     command(2,
751     SCHEDULED_TIME,\01:59:55\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
752     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6DumpDataToVR4_004: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"",
753     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
754 ),
755     note(1,
756     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
757     TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6DumpDataToVR4_004: data volume in VR4 0.638 Gibit.\"",
758     ),
759     end;
760
761     request(VIR_VH2_C6openCover_005,
762     START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_072+00:45:00,
763     TITLE, "VIR open cover",
764     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
765     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
766     KEY, "No_Key")
767
768     activity(1,
769     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
770     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6openCover_005: Set for opening the cover.\"",
771     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
772     ),
773     end;
774
775     request(VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_005,
776     START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_072+00:47:00,
777     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
778     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
779     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
780     KEY, "No_Key")
781
782     command(1,
783     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
784     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_005: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
785     frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"",
786     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
787     ),
788     command(2,
789     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
790     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"",
791     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_005: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"",
792     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
793     ),
794     command(3,
795     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
796     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_005: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"",
797     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
798     ),
799     note(1,
800     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
801     TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_005: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.174 Gibit\"",
802     ),
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802  command(4,
803  SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
804  NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_005: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
      frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
805  VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
806  ),
807  command(5,
808  SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
809  COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
810  NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_005: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
811  VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
812  ),
813  command(6,
814  SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
815  NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_005: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
816  VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
817  ),
818  note(2,
819  SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
820  TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_005: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.348 Gibit"\
821  ),
822  command(7,
823  SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
824  NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_005: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
      frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
825  VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
826  ),
827  command(8,
828  SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
829  COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
830  NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_005: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
831  VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
832  ),
833  command(9,
834  SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
835  NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_005: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
836  VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
837  ),
838  note(3,
839  SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
840  TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_005: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.522 Gibit"\
841  ),
842  command(10,
843  SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
844  NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_005: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
      frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
845  VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
846  ),
847  command(11,
848  SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
849  COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
850  NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_005: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
851  VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
852  ),
853  command(12,

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854     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
855     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_005: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
856     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
857   ),
858   note(4,
859     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
860     TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_005: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 0.696 Gibit\"\\
861   ),
862   command(13,
863     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
864     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_005: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
      frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\\,
865     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
866   ),
867   command(14,
868     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
869     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
870     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_005: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
871     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
872   ),
873   command(15,
874     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
875     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_005: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
876     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
877   ),
878   note(5,
879     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
880     TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_005: Cube N.5 Data Volume in MM 0.870 Gibit\"\\
881   ),
882 end;
883
884 request(VIR_VH2_C6CloseCover_005,
885   START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_072+01:33:00,
886   TITLE, "VIR close cover",
887   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
888   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
889   KEY, "No_Key")
890
891 activity(1,
892   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
893   NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6CloseCover_005: Set for closing the cover.\"\\,
894   VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"CLOSE")
895   ),
896 end;
897
898 request(VIR_VH2_C6DumpDataToVR4_005,
899   START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_072+01:35:00,
900   TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",
901   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
902   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
903   KEY, "No_Key")
904
905 command(1,
906   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
907   NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6DumpDataToVR4_005: begin data dumping into VR4.\"\\,
908   VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
909   ),
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910  command(2,
911    SCHEDULED_TIME,\01:59:55\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
912    NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6DumpDataToVR4_005: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
913    VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
914  ),
915  note(1,
916    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
917    TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6DumpDataToVR4_005: data volume in VR4 0.637 Gibit.\"\\
918  ),
919  end;
920
921  request(VIR_VH2_C60penCover_006,
922    START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_073+00:45:00,
923    TITLE, \"VIR open cover\",
924    REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
925    PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
926    KEY, \"No_Key\")
927
928  activity(1,
929    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
930    NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C60penCover_006: Set for opening the cover.\"\\,
931    VIR_Cover(vir_cover,\"OPEN\")
932  ),
933  end;
934
935  request(VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_006,
936    START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_073+00:47:00,
937    TITLE, \"VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.\",
938    REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
939    PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
940    KEY, \"No_Key\")
941
942  command(1,
943    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
944    NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_006: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\\,
945    VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\", \"0N\",10,\"NO_VIR_TM
946  ),
947  command(2,
948    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
949    COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
950    NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_006: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
951    VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
952  ),
953  command(3,
954    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
955    NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_006: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
956    VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
957  ),
958  note(1,
959    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
960    TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_006: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.174 Gibit\"\\
961  ),
962  command(4,
963    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
964    NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_006: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\\,
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965     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
966 ),
967     command(5,
968     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
969     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\,
970     NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_006: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\,
971     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
972 ),
973     command(6,
974     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
975     NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_006: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\",
976     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
977 ),
978     note(2,
979     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
980     TEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_006: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.348 Gibit\"\
981 ),
982     command(7,
983     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
984     NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_006: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\,
985     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
986 ),
987     command(8,
988     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
989     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\,
990     NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_006: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\,
991     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
992 ),
993     command(9,
994     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
995     NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_006: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\",
996     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
997 ),
998     note(3,
999     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1000    TEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_006: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.522 Gibit\"\
1001 ),
1002    command(10,
1003    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1004    NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_006: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\,
1005    VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1006 ),
1007    command(11,
1008    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1009    COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\,
1010    NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_006: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\,
1011    VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1012 ),
1013    command(12,
1014    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1015    NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_006: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\",
1016    VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1017 ),
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1018 note(4,
1019   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1020   TEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_006: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 0.696 Gibit"\
1021   ),
1022   command(13,
1023     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1024     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_006: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
1025     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1026   ),
1027   command(14,
1028     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1029     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
1030     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_006: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1031     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1032   ),
1033   command(15,
1034     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1035     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_006: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
1036     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1037   ),
1038   note(5,
1039     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1040     TEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_006: Cube N.5 Data Volume in MM 0.870 Gibit"\
1041     ),
1042   end;
1043
1044   request(VIR_VH2_C6CloseCover_006,
1045     START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_073+01:33:00,
1046     TITLE, "VIR close cover",
1047     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1048     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1049     KEY, "No_Key")
1050
1051   activity(1,
1052     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1053     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C6CloseCover_006: Set for closing the cover."\",
1054     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"CLOSE")
1055   ),
1056   end;
1057
1058   request(VIR_VH2_C6DumpDataToVR4_006,
1059     START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_073+01:35:00,
1060     TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",
1061     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1062     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1063     KEY, "No_Key")
1064
1065   command(1,
1066     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1067     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C6DumpDataToVR4_006: begin data dumping into VR4."\",
1068     VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
1069   ),
1070   command(2,
1071     SCHEDULED_TIME,\01:59:55\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1072     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C6DumpDataToVR4_006: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
1073     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()

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1074 ),
1075 note(1,
1076   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1077   TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6DumpDataToVR4_006: data volume in VR4 0.637 Gibit.\"\\
1078 ),
1079 end;
1080
1081 request(VIR_VH2_C60penCover_007,
1082   START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_074+00:45:00,
1083   TITLE, \"VIR open cover\",
1084   REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
1085   PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
1086   KEY, \"No_Key\")
1087
1088 activity(1,
1089   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1090   NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C60penCover_007: Set for opening the cover.\"\\,
1091   VIR_Cover(vir_cover,\"OPEN\")
1092 ),
1093 end;
1094
1095 request(VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_007,
1096   START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_074+00:47:00,
1097   TITLE, \"VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.\",
1098   REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
1099   PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
1100   KEY, \"No_Key\")
1101
1102 command(1,
1103   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1104   NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_007: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
1105     frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\\,
1106   VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR_TM
1107 ),
1108 command(2,
1109   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1110   COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
1111   NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_007: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
1112   VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
1113 ),
1114 command(3,
1115   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1116   NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_007: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1117   VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1118 ),
1119 note(1,
1120   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1121   TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_007: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.174 Gibit\"\\
1122 ),
1123 command(4,
1124   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1125   NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_007: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
1126     frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\\,
1127   VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR_TM
1128 ),
1129 command(5,
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1128 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1129 COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
1130 NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_007: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
1131 VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
1132 ),
1133 command(6,
1134 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1135 NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_007: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1136 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1137 ),
1138 note(2,
1139 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1140 TEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_007: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.348 Gibit\"\\
1141 ),
1142 command(7,
1143 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1144 NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_007: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\\,
1145 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR_TM
1146 ),
1147 command(8,
1148 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1149 COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
1150 NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_007: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
1151 VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
1152 ),
1153 command(9,
1154 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1155 NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_007: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1156 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1157 ),
1158 note(3,
1159 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1160 TEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_007: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.522 Gibit\"\\
1161 ),
1162 command(10,
1163 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1164 NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_007: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\\,
1165 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR_TM
1166 ),
1167 command(11,
1168 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1169 COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
1170 NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_007: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
1171 VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
1172 ),
1173 command(12,
1174 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1175 NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_007: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1176 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1177 ),
1178 note(4,
1179 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1180 TEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_007: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 0.696 Gibit\"\\
1181 ),
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1182  command(13,
1183    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1184    NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_007: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
    frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
1185    VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1186  ),
1187  command(14,
1188    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1189    COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
1190    NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_007: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1191    VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1192  ),
1193  command(15,
1194    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1195    NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_007: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
1196    VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1197  ),
1198  note(5,
1199    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1200    TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_007: Cube N.5 Data Volume in MM 0.870 Gibit"\
1201  ),
1202  end;
1203
1204  request(VIR_VH2_C6CloseCover_007,
1205    START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_074+01:33:00,
1206    TITLE, "VIR cclose cover",
1207    REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1208    PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1209    KEY, "No_Key")
1210
1211  activity(1,
1212    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1213    NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6CloseCover_007: Set for closing the cover."\",
1214    VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"CLOSE")
1215  ),
1216  end;
1217
1218  request(VIR_VH2_C6DumpDataToVR4_007,
1219    START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_074+01:35:00,
1220    TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",
1221    REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1222    PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1223    KEY, "No_Key")
1224
1225  command(1,
1226    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1227    NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6DumpDataToVR4_007: begin data dumping into VR4."\",
1228    VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
1229  ),
1230  command(2,
1231    SCHEDULED_TIME,\01:59:55\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1232    NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6DumpDataToVR4_007: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
1233    VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1234  ),
1235  note(1,
1236    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1237    TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6DumpDataToVR4_007: data volume in VR4 0.637 Gibit."\"

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1238 ),
1239 end;
1240
1241 request(VIR_VH2_C60penCover_008,
1242     START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_075+00:45:00,
1243     TITLE, "VIR open cover",
1244     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1245     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1246     KEY, "No_Key")
1247
1248 activity(1,
1249     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1250     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C60penCover_008: Set for opening the cover." \,
1251     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
1252 ),
1253 end;
1254
1255 request(VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_008,
1256     START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_075+00:47:00,
1257     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
1258     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1259     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1260     KEY, "No_Key")
1261
1262 command(1,
1263     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1264     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_008: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s" \,
1265     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1266 ),
1267 command(2,
1268     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1269     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714" \,
1270     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_008: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode" \,
1271     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1272 ),
1273 command(3,
1274     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1275     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_008: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
1276     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1277 ),
1278 note(1,
1279     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1280     TEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_008: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.174 Gibit" \
1281 ),
1282 command(4,
1283     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1284     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_008: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s" \,
1285     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1286 ),
1287 command(5,
1288     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1289     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714" \,
1290     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_008: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode" \,
1291     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")

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1292 ),
1293   command(6,
1294     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1295     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_008: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1296     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1297   ),
1298   note(2,
1299     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1300     TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_008: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.348 Gibit"\\
1301   ),
1302   command(7,
1303     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1304     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_008: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
1305     frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\\,
1306     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1307   ),
1308   command(8,
1309     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1310     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\\,
1311     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_008: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\\,
1312     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1313   ),
1314   command(9,
1315     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1316     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_008: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1317     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1318   ),
1319   note(3,
1320     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1321     TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_008: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.522 Gibit"\\
1322   ),
1323   command(10,
1324     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1325     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_008: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
1326     frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\\,
1327     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1328   ),
1329   command(11,
1330     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1331     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\\,
1332     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_008: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\\,
1333     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1334   ),
1335   command(12,
1336     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1337     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_008: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1338     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1339   ),
1340   note(4,
1341     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1342     TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_008: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 0.696 Gibit"\\
1343   ),
1344   command(13,
1345     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1346     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_008: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
1347     frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\\,
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1345     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1346 ),
1347     command(14,
1348     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1349     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
1350     NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_008: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
1351     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1352 ),
1353     command(15,
1354     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1355     NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_008: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1356     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1357 ),
1358     note(5,
1359     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1360     TEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_008: Cube N.5 Data Volume in MM 0.870 Gibit\"\\
1361 ),
1362 end;
1363
1364 request(VIR_VH2_C6CloseCover_008,
1365     START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_075+01:33:00,
1366     TITLE, "VIR close cover",
1367     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1368     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1369     KEY, "No_Key")
1370
1371 activity(1,
1372     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1373     NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C6CloseCover_008: Set for closing the cover.\"\\,
1374     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"CLOSE")
1375 ),
1376 end;
1377
1378 request(VIR_VH2_C6DumpDataToVR4_008,
1379     START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_075+01:35:00,
1380     TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",
1381     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1382     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1383     KEY, "No_Key")
1384
1385 command(1,
1386     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1387     NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C6DumpDataToVR4_008: begin data dumping into VR4.\"\\,
1388     VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
1389 ),
1390 command(2,
1391     SCHEDULED_TIME,\01:59:55\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1392     NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C6DumpDataToVR4_008: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1393     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1394 ),
1395     note(1,
1396     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1397     TEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C6DumpDataToVR4_008: data volume in VR4 1.212 Gibit.\"\\
1398 ),
1399 end;
1400
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1401 request(VIR_VH2_C6openCover_009,
1402     START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_076+00:45:00,
1403     TITLE, "VIR open cover",
1404     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1405     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1406     KEY, "No_Key")
1407
1408 activity(1,
1409     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1410     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C6openCover_009: Set for opening the cover."\,
1411     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
1412 ),
1413 end;
1414
1415 request(VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_009,
1416     START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_076+00:47:00,
1417     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
1418     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1419     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1420     KEY, "No_Key")
1421
1422 command(1,
1423     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1424     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_009: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
1425     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1426 ),
1427 command(2,
1428     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1429     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
1430     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_009: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1431     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1432 ),
1433 command(3,
1434     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1435     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_009: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
1436     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1437 ),
1438 note(1,
1439     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1440     TEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_009: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.174 Gibit"\
1441 ),
1442 command(4,
1443     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1444     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_009: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
1445     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1446 ),
1447 command(5,
1448     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1449     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
1450     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_009: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1451     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1452 ),
1453 command(6,
1454     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,

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1455 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_009: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\",
1456 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1457 ),
1458 note(2,
1459 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1460 TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_009: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.348 Gibit\"\
1461 ),
1462 command(7,
1463 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1464 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_009: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\,
1465 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1466 ),
1467 command(8,
1468 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1469 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\,
1470 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_009: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\,
1471 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1472 ),
1473 command(9,
1474 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1475 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_009: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\",
1476 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1477 ),
1478 note(3,
1479 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1480 TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_009: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.522 Gibit\"\
1481 ),
1482 command(10,
1483 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1484 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_009: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\,
1485 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1486 ),
1487 command(11,
1488 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1489 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\,
1490 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_009: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\,
1491 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1492 ),
1493 command(12,
1494 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1495 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_009: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\",
1496 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1497 ),
1498 note(4,
1499 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1500 TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_009: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 0.696 Gibit\"\
1501 ),
1502 command(13,
1503 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1504 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_009: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\,
1505 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1506 ),
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1507  command(14,
1508    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1509    COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
1510    NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_009: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
1511    VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
1512  ),
1513  command(15,
1514    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1515    NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_009: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1516    VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1517  ),
1518  note(5,
1519    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1520    TEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_009: Cube N.5 Data Volume in MM 0.870 Gibit\"\\
1521  ),
1522  end;
1523
1524  request(VIR_VH2_C6CloseCover_009,
1525    START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_076+01:33:00,
1526    TITLE, \"VIR close cover\",
1527    REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
1528    PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
1529    KEY, \"No_Key\")
1530
1531  activity(1,
1532    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1533    NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C6CloseCover_009: Set for closing the cover.\"\\,
1534    VIR_Cover(vir_cover,\"CLOSE\")
1535  ),
1536  end;
1537
1538  request(VIR_VH2_C6DumpDataToVR4_009,
1539    START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_076+01:35:00,
1540    TITLE, \"VIR dump data into VR4\",
1541    REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
1542    PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
1543    KEY, \"No_Key\")
1544
1545  command(1,
1546    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1547    NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C6DumpDataToVR4_009: begin data dumping into VR4.\"\\,
1548    VIR_MM_DUMP(\"LOSSLESS\")
1549  ),
1550  command(2,
1551    SCHEDULED_TIME,\01:59:55\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1552    NTEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C6DumpDataToVR4_009: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1553    VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1554  ),
1555  note(1,
1556    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1557    TEXT,\"VIR_VH2_C6DumpDataToVR4_009: data volume in VR4 1.079 Gibit.\"\\
1558  ),
1559  end;
1560
1561  request(VIR_VH2_C6OpenCover_010,
1562    START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_077+00:45:00,
1563    TITLE, \"VIR open cover\",
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1564 REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1565 PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1566 KEY, "No_Key")
1567
1568 activity(1,
1569   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1570   NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C6openCover_010: Set for opening the cover."\,
1571   VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
1572 ),
1573 end;
1574
1575 request(VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_010,
1576   START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_077+00:47:00,
1577   TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
1578   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1579   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1580   KEY, "No_Key")
1581
1582 command(1,
1583   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1584   NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_010: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
1585   VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1586 ),
1587 command(2,
1588   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1589   COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
1590   NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_010: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1591   VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1592 ),
1593 command(3,
1594   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1595   NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_010: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
1596   VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1597 ),
1598 note(1,
1599   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1600   TEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_010: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.174 Gibit"\
1601 ),
1602 command(4,
1603   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1604   NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_010: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
1605   VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1606 ),
1607 command(5,
1608   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1609   COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
1610   NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_010: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1611   VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1612 ),
1613 command(6,
1614   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1615   NTEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_010: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
1616   VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1617 ),

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1618 note(2,  
1619   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1620   TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_010: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.348 Gibit\"\  
1621 ),  
1622 command(7,  
1623   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1624   NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_010: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50  
frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\  
1625   VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR_TM  
1626 ),  
1627 command(8,  
1628   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1629   COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\  
1630   NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_010: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\  
1631   VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")  
1632 ),  
1633 command(9,  
1634   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1635   NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_010: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\  
1636   VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
1637 ),  
1638 note(3,  
1639   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1640   TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_010: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.522 Gibit\"\  
1641 ),  
1642 command(10,  
1643   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1644   NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_010: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50  
frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\  
1645   VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR_TM  
1646 ),  
1647 command(11,  
1648   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1649   COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\  
1650   NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_010: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\  
1651   VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")  
1652 ),  
1653 command(12,  
1654   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1655   NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_010: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\  
1656   VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
1657 ),  
1658 note(4,  
1659   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1660   TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_010: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 0.696 Gibit\"\  
1661 ),  
1662 command(13,  
1663   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1664   NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_010: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50  
frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\  
1665   VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR_TM  
1666 ),  
1667 command(14,  
1668   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1669   COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\  

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1670 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_010: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,  
1671 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")  
1672 ),  
1673 command(15,  
1674 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1675 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_010: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\  
1676 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
1677 ),  
1678 note(5,  
1679 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1680 TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6PushBroomToVIR_010: Cube N.5 Data Volume in MM 0.870 Gibit"\  
1681 ),  
1682 end;  
1683  
1684 request(VIR_VH2_C6CloseCover_010,  
1685 START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_077+01:33:00,  
1686 TITLE, "VIR close cover",  
1687 REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
1688 PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
1689 KEY, "No_Key")  
1690  
1691 activity(1,  
1692 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
1693 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6CloseCover_010: Set for closing the cover."\  
1694 VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"CLOSE")  
1695 ),  
1696 end;  
1697  
1698 request(VIR_VH2_C6DumpDataToVR4_010,  
1699 START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_077+01:35:00,  
1700 TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",  
1701 REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
1702 PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
1703 KEY, "No_Key")  
1704  
1705 command(1,  
1706 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
1707 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6DumpDataToVR4_010: begin data dumping into VR4."\  
1708 VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")  
1709 ),  
1710 command(2,  
1711 SCHEDULED_TIME,\01:59:55\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1712 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6DumpDataToVR4_010: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\  
1713 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
1714 ),  
1715 note(1,  
1716 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1717 TEXT,\\"VIR_VH2_C6DumpDataToVR4_010: data volume in VR4 0.809 Gibit."\  
1718 ),  
1719 end;  
1720  
1721 request(VIR_VH2_C6PowerOff_010,  
1722 START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_077+03:36:00,  
1723 TITLE, "VIR Power off",  
1724 REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
1725 PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
1726 KEY, "No_Key")
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1727
1728  note(1,
1729    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1730    TEXT,\ "VIR_VH2_C6PowerOff_010: Power off VIR instrument." \
1731  ),
1732  spawn(1,
1733    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1734    REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\,
1735    RT_on_board_block(vpof_vir_power_off)
1736  ),
1737  end;
1738
1739  request(VIR_VH2_VMLEND_C6HAMO2,
1740    START_TIME, VH2_DLTERM_077+03:40:00,
1741    TITLE, "VIR Sequence End - vir_vh2_C6HAMO2 (ds122)",
1742    REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1743    PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1744    KEY, "No_Key")
1745
1746  note(1,
1747    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1748    TEXT,\ "End sequence ds122 - vir_vh2_C6HAMO2" \
1749  ),
1750  end;
1751
1752  $$EOF
```